

Applied Project Report

TITLE:

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN STREAMLINING MARINE RADIO INSPECTIONS

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Declaration of Originality

I, Kok Khiang Lim, hereby declare that the work presented in this MSc Applied Project report, titled “The Role of Digital Tools in Streamlining Marine Radio Inspections,” is my own original work. All sources of information have been duly acknowledged through appropriate references. I confirm that this work has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification at Middlesex University or any other institution.

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Abstract

Marine radio inspections – such as testing Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) equipment – are critical for vessel safety and regulatory compliance, yet traditional inspection methods are largely manual and paper-based, making them time-consuming and error-prone. This applied project investigated how digital tools can streamline these inspection processes. It evaluated current practices and the extent of digital tool adoption, identified efficiency gains and other benefits from using digital inspection technologies, and examined the barriers hindering their wider implementation, in order to inform practical recommendations. A mixed-methods approach was used, combining an online survey of marine radio inspection stakeholders with follow-up semi-structured interviews for deeper insight. The survey quantified digital tool usage rates, perceived impacts on inspection performance, and implementation challenges, while the interviews with inspectors and maritime officials provided qualitative context to explain the survey trends. Results indicated a growing uptake of digital inspection tools, with approximately 72% of survey respondents using such technologies. These users reported faster inspections, fewer data recording errors, and improved compliance tracking through centralized digital records, and overall they expressed high satisfaction with the tools (citing features like real-time data capture and automated reporting as key advantages). However, the study also revealed persistent barriers to full adoption: insufficient training and digital skills, resistance to change in established

practices, and resource constraints (e.g. costs and technical issues) were the most common challenges, alongside some concerns about regulatory acceptance of digital records and cybersecurity risks. In conclusion, while digital tools can significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of marine radio inspections, realizing these benefits industry-wide requires overcoming the identified barriers. The findings underscore the need for targeted training, change management efforts, and supportive policies to help maritime stakeholders adopt and integrate digital inspection tools, ultimately contributing to safer and more efficient operations.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Context

Maritime safety relies on effective ship-to-shore and ship-to-ship communication, especially during emergencies. International regulations like the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Convention require all passenger ships and cargo ships over 300 gross tonnages on international voyages to carry and maintain functional radio equipment under the Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) framework (IMO, 2014). To ensure this critical equipment remains operational, vessels undergo an initial radio survey and annual inspections as part of the Harmonized System of Survey and Certification (HSSC) regime (IMO, 2021). These surveys are conducted by authorized radio surveyors who verify that the ship's communication equipment meets all required regulations and performance standards. If the ship meets requirements, a Safety Radio Certificate is issued; if not, deficiencies are documented for correction.

GMDSS radio inspections are meticulous, covering both documentation and hardware. Surveyors confirm that required documents (radio licenses, operator certificates, previous survey reports, etc.) are on board and valid, then test each piece of GMDSS equipment to ensure proper functionality (GMDSS Testers, n.d.). Key components inspected include VHF and MF/HF radios, satellite communication terminals, Emergency Position-Indicating Radio Beacons (EPIRBs), Search and Rescue Transponders (SARTs), Automatic Identification Systems (AIS), and NAVTEX receivers (Shiptron, n.d.). In practice, modern surveyors use multi-function test devices to verify signal frequency, transmission power, receiver sensitivity and other parameters against IMO and ITU performance standards, with results automatically logged for consistency (GMDSS Testers, n.d.). These digital tools have largely replaced older, purely manual instruments, improving the reliability and efficiency of inspections.

Despite these technological aids, many aspects of the inspection workflow have traditionally remained paper based. Until recently, survey findings were written on

paper forms and narrative reports – a process prone to delays, human error, and inconsistent detail (DNV, 2020). Over the past decade, the industry has begun adopting digital solutions to streamline inspections. Surveyors now use tablet-based applications to capture data (including photos and audio notes as evidence) in real time, which can be instantly shared with onshore managers via cloud platforms for faster review (DNV, 2020). Classification societies such as DNV have reported that electronic inspection reports produce more consistent results and richer data for analysis than manual paperwork (DNV, 2020). The push for remote surveys was also accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic: what began as an emergency measure has become a broader trend, with classification societies expanding remote survey capabilities using advanced communication technologies. When approved by flag States, certain parts of radio surveys can now be carried out remotely, yielding flexibility and efficiency gains without compromising safety (Bureau Veritas, 2020; IACS, 2020).

Against this backdrop, major maritime stakeholders – including the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and IACS – are increasingly advocating digital tools to enhance compliance and efficiency. For example, IACS introduced a unified requirement for remote surveys (UR Z29) to ensure technology-assisted inspections uphold the same standards as traditional onboard surveys (IACS, 2020). These efforts align with broader “smart ship” and e-Navigation initiatives that promote electronic record-keeping and data exchange for safety. In summary, this background highlights the safety-critical nature of marine radio surveys and the growing momentum toward leveraging digital solutions to streamline these processes.

1.2 Problem Statement and Rationale

Despite the availability of modern technology, marine radio inspection practices remain largely manual and have significant shortcomings. Traditional GMDSS radio surveys are time-consuming and labour-intensive, relying on paper checklists and reports that are prone to human error and omissions. This lack of digital integration means inspectors may miss opportunities to improve consistency and efficiency. In

practice, many surveyors still record results by hand, which leads to inconsistent reporting and makes it difficult to aggregate or analyse findings (DNV, 2020). Without electronic records, recurring equipment issues may go unnoticed, and communicating urgent findings to onshore management is slower. Coordinating in-person inspections across different ports can also be cumbersome and costly, often causing scheduling delays for ship operators.

These challenges have clear safety and compliance implications. If a critical radio device is not properly inspected or maintained, it might fail during an emergency – for example, an emergency beacon could be inoperative without anyone realizing it until a distress situation arises. Port State Control inspections regularly discover GMDSS deficiencies, indicating that current methods do not always ensure full readiness. Maintaining all radio systems in constant working order is difficult with purely manual checks. Meanwhile, the maritime industry faces pressure to boost efficiency and embrace digital transformation. Other inspection domains – from hull and machinery checks to safety equipment audits – have begun using digital aids (drones for structural surveys, electronic logbooks for records, etc.), showing that traditional surveys can be modernized to good effect. Therefore, it is timely to investigate how digital tools could enhance radio survey processes. Little research to date has examined digitalization in the marine radio inspection context, so it remains uncertain how much these tools can improve compliance or efficiency and what barriers might hinder their adoption (such as regulations, training, or cost). In sum, marine radio inspections in their current form are not fully keeping pace with modern capabilities, and this research is driven by the opportunity to leverage digital technology to improve safety, compliance, and efficiency in maritime operations.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to investigate how digital tools can streamline GMDSS marine radio inspections in order to improve regulatory compliance, inspection efficiency, and overall maritime safety. To achieve this aim, the study will pursue the following objectives:

1. **Review the regulatory and operational framework:** Examine the current requirements and practices for GMDSS radio inspections under international conventions and guidelines (e.g. SOLAS, IMO resolutions) and classification society rules, to establish a baseline of the existing survey regime (IMO, 2021).
2. **Identify applicable digital tools and technologies:** Identify the range of digital tools (hardware and software) available or emerging for marine radio inspections (e.g. multi-functional test devices, electronic inspection software, data management systems, and remote inspection methods).
3. **Evaluate impacts on compliance, efficiency, and safety:** Assess the extent to which digital-assisted inspection methods could improve regulatory compliance, increase operational efficiency (such as saving time, reducing paperwork, and simplifying scheduling), and enhance safety (by improving the reliability of distress communication equipment and enabling more proactive maintenance).
4. **Identify implementation challenges and enablers:** Investigate potential challenges that might hinder the adoption of digital tools in radio surveys (e.g. regulatory restrictions requiring physical attendance, resistance to change or lack of digital skills among personnel, connectivity limitations at sea, and upfront costs). Likewise, identify factors that would enable implementation (such as supportive regulatory developments, industry initiatives, or demonstrated success stories) to understand how wider adoption could be encouraged.
5. **Provide recommendations for practice and further research:** Formulate recommendations on best practices for integrating digital tools into marine radio inspections, to guide maritime regulators, classification societies, and ship operators in leveraging technology for better compliance and safety. Also identify areas for further development or study (such as technological innovations or policy updates) to support the continued digital transformation of maritime surveys.

1.4 Scope and Significance

Scope: This research focuses on the inspection of GMDSS radio communication equipment on SOLAS-regulated vessels (primarily passenger and cargo ships in international service). It examines the standard radio survey process mandated by international regulations and classification society rules and remains confined to radio inspection activities (as opposed to other survey areas like hull or machinery). The perspective is global, drawing on International Maritime Organization (IMO) requirements and IACS guidelines. Both hardware and software-based digital tools fall within scope – for example, multi-function test sets, digital inspection checklists, and remote survey techniques – but the study does not address the engineering design of the radio equipment itself, focusing instead on the inspection tools and procedures. The emphasis is on current practices and near-term developments (circa 2010s–2020s).

Significance: The findings of this project carry importance for maritime industry practice and for academic study of maritime safety management. In industry terms, incorporating digital tools into radio surveys could enhance safety by ensuring that distress communication equipment is reliably tested and maintained, thereby reducing the chance of critical failures going unnoticed and directly supporting SOLAS objectives. More efficient inspections should also translate into fewer detentions or delays, yielding operational and economic benefits for operators. The study further shows how a traditional compliance process can evolve through digital innovation, aligning with broader initiatives for electronic documentation and remote audits. The recommendations can inform regulators and classification societies as they update policies or guidelines to accommodate digital inspection methods (such as acceptance of electronic certificates or remote survey results) without compromising safety standards.

Academically, this research addresses a clear gap: while most maritime digitalization research has focused on navigation, autonomy, and big-data applications, little has addressed digitalizing compliance inspections. By examining the GMDSS radio survey process, the study contributes to maritime operations management and safety

literature by providing insight into how technology can improve a specific safety-critical inspection regime. Its interdisciplinary scope – spanning regulatory compliance, technical tool use, and organizational change – means the results should interest multiple stakeholders. Overall, the project will help stakeholders balance technological innovation with strict safety requirements, and it lays groundwork for further research into digital survey processes.

1.5 Structure of the Report

The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2: Literature Review** – Reviews relevant regulations, current marine radio inspection practices, and prior studies on digital tools, establishing the study’s background and identifying knowledge gaps.
- **Chapter 3: Research Methodology** – Outlines the research design and describes the methods of data collection (e.g. case studies, interviews, surveys) and analysis, including considerations of validity and ethics.
- **Chapter 4: Results and Analysis** – Presents the research results, organized by objective, and analyses them to reveal key insights into efficiency gains, compliance outcomes, and implementation challenges.
- **Chapter 5: Discussion** – Discusses the findings relative to the research aim and the literature, evaluates how well each objective was achieved, and considers their significance for industry practice.
- **Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations** – Summarizes how the research aim was met, offers recommendations for regulators, classification societies, and ship operators, and notes the study’s limitations and areas for future research.

2. Literature Review

This chapter critically reviews relevant literature and industry sources across five key areas. Section 2.1 covers the context of marine radio inspections and the governing regulatory frameworks (e.g. SOLAS and GMDSS requirements). Section 2.2 discusses broader digital transformation trends in maritime operations. Section 2.3 reviews theoretical models of technology adoption (including the Technology Acceptance Model, Diffusion of Innovations, and change management perspectives) to frame how new tools are adopted. Section 2.4 surveys empirical studies and industry cases on implementing digital inspection tools in maritime contexts, highlighting reported benefits and challenges. Finally, Section 2.5 identifies gaps in current research and introduces the conceptual framework developed from the literature, which will guide the analysis in later chapters.

2.1 Marine Radio Inspections & Regulatory Frameworks

Marine radio inspections are a critical safety requirement in the maritime industry, mandated by international regulations. Under the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) 1974 (as amended), all passenger ships (regardless of size) and cargo ships of 300 gross tonnage and above on international voyages must carry radio communications equipment compliant with the Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS). These ships are subject to an initial radio survey and periodic inspections of their radio installations to ensure continuous operational readiness. In practice, this is implemented via the Cargo Ship Safety Radio Certificate (for cargo vessels) or included in the Passenger Ship Safety Certificate, each valid up to five years with annual endorsements in between (i.e. annual radio surveys). Thus, an Annual Safety Radio Survey must be carried out each year by a qualified radio inspector, following standards set by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and flag state authorities. The inspections are typically performed by authorized personnel (often classification society surveyors or other inspectors recognized by the flag state) in accordance with IMO's Harmonized System of Survey and Certification (HSSC) guidelines. The IMO's Survey Guidelines under the HSSC (e.g. IMO Resolution A.1156(32)) adopted in

2021) standardize how surveys are conducted and ensure that the annual GMDSS radio inspection is thorough and consistent internationally (IMO, 2021).

Marine radio inspections serve to verify that all required GMDSS equipment is present, properly installed, and functioning in accordance with SOLAS and IMO performance standards. SOLAS Chapter IV (Radiocommunications) specifies the functional requirements and equipment carriage depending on the ship’s sea area of operation (Sea Areas A1 through A4 under GMDSS). In general, Sea Area A1 covers coastal VHF range, A2 covers the MF range beyond A1, A3 spans the Inmarsat satellite footprint (excluding polar regions), and A4 covers the high-latitude polar regions beyond Inmarsat coverage. Accordingly, ships must carry an appropriate combination of VHF, MF/HF radio, satellite communication terminals, and other subsystems (such as NAVTEX receivers, Emergency Position-Indicating Radio Beacons [EPIRBs], and Search and Rescue Transponders [SARTs]) based on their certified sea areas. GMDSS regulations thus ensure that a distress alert can be sent from anywhere at sea by some means, whether terrestrial or satellite radio. Table 2.1 provides a summary of the main GMDSS equipment required and key inspection points for each item.

Equipment	Required For	Inspection Requirements
VHF Radio w/ DSC (Digital Selective Calling)	All SOLAS ships (Sea Areas A1–A4)	Verify operation on Channel 16 and other emergency channels; test DSC distress alert (Channel 70) and DSC watch receiver; ensure power is supplied from main, emergency, and reserve sources; conduct an on-air contact test with a coast station or another ship to confirm transmit/receive functionality (IMO, 2021; GMDSS Testers, 2024).
MF Radio w/ DSC	Ships operating in Sea Areas A2–A4	Test the MF transmitter/receiver on the standard distress frequency (2187.5 kHz); check tuning across the MF band; verify DSC watch function; confirm the availability of a redundant power supply (IMO, 2021).

Equipment	Required For	Inspection Requirements
HF Radio with DSC (or combined MF/HF)	Ships in Sea Areas A3 (if no satellite coverage) and A4	Test HF transmitter on designated distress frequencies (e.g. 8414.5 kHz DSC); verify capability for narrow-band direct printing (NBDP) distress messaging; confirm adequate receiver sensitivity and coverage for the operating area (IMO, 2021).
Inmarsat C Terminal (Satellite SES)	Sea Area A3 as an alternative to MF/HF for non-polar regions	Confirm the terminal can send/receive distress alerts via satellite; verify registration details and correct terminal ID; perform a test distress message; ensure continuous GPS input for automatic inclusion of ship position (IMO, 2021).
406 MHz EPIRB (Emergency Position-Indicating Radio Beacon)	All SOLAS ships (covering all Sea Areas A1–A4)	Conduct an annual performance test using an appropriate EPIRB tester; check the encoded identity and location data, signal strength, and frequency stability; ensure battery and hydrostatic release expiry dates are valid; verify that the EPIRB is mounted in a float-free bracket (SOLAS Chapter IV, 2021; GMDSS Testers, 2024).
SART or AIS-SART	All SOLAS ships (minimum number dependent on vessel type, e.g., one unit for ships 300–499 GT, two units for ships \geq 500 GT or any passenger vessel)	Inspect physical condition and mounting; verify battery expiry and overall operational status using the self-test functionality; for AIS-SART, check that the distress signal is transmitted correctly (IMO, 2021).

Equipment	Required For	Inspection Requirements
NAVTEX Receiver (or EGC Receiver for Inmarsat SafetyNet)	Ships in Sea Areas A1–A3 (for Maritime Safety Information broadcasts)	Ensure that the receiver is correctly tuned to NAVTEX frequencies and receiving Safety Information; verify signal clarity by checking a recent NAVTEX message printout or digital log; for EGC receivers, confirm that SafetyNet messages are received reliably (IMO, 2021).
Two-way VHF Portable Radios (for survival craft)	All SOLAS ships (requirements vary: typically, 2 units for 300–499 GT and 3 units for ≥500 GT or passenger ships)	Test the operation of the portable VHF radios on Channel 16 (and other necessary channels); ensure spare batteries or charging units are available and within expiry (IMO, 2021).
Reserve Power Supply (GMDSS-dedicated batteries and/or emergency generator)	All SOLAS ships (covering Sea Areas A1–A4)	Inspect the dedicated GMDSS battery installation to ensure it supplies sufficient emergency power (e.g. 1 hour when a generator is available, or 6 hours if not); check battery condition (voltage, specific gravity for wet cells); confirm that chargers and emergency generators, if provided, are operational with automatic start capabilities (SOLAS II-1/42 & II-1/43; IMO, 2021).

Table 2.1: Summary of GMDSS Equipment and Key Inspection Checks

(References: IMO, 2021; SOLAS Chapter IV, 2021; GMDSS Testers, 2024)

During an inspection, the surveyor methodically checks both documentation and equipment. The process, summarized in Figure 2.1, begins with pre-survey preparation (e.g. reviewing prior survey reports and any special instructions) and a documentation check, followed by the physical inspection and testing of each piece of equipment, and finally issuance of the survey report or certificate. Any deficiencies identified must be rectified before the Safety Radio Certificate can be

endorsed or renewed; often minor issues can be corrected on the spot or within a short grace period.

Figure 2.1: *Typical GMDSS Safety Radio Survey process under SOLAS. The inspector first reviews documentation (equipment certificates, radio logs, etc.), then tests the GMDSS equipment (power supplies, radios, EPIRB, etc.). If deficiencies are found, they must be rectified and the equipment retested. Once all is in order, a survey report is issued, and the Safety Radio Certificate is endorsed.*

In the equipment-testing phase, the surveyor verifies that all GMDSS components meet their performance requirements. For example, the VHF radio is checked on the required distress channels and its Digital Selective Calling (DSC) function is tested (typically by sending a test alert on Channel 70 or conducting an on-air communication test). The MF/HF radio is similarly tested by transmitting a DSC test call or establishing voice contact with a coast station, and an Inmarsat-C terminal might be tested by sending a brief message to a shore station. Critical safety devices like the EPIRB and SART are tested in self-test modes to avoid emitting false distress signals. The surveyor also examines installation arrangements – for instance, antenna placement, cable condition, and dedicated GMDSS battery installations – to ensure they comply with regulations and are in good order. Upon successful completion of all checks, the inspector issues an updated Safety Radio Survey Report and endorses the Safety Radio Certificate, confirming the ship’s compliance for another year.

In summary, marine radio inspections are a well-established, stringent process grounded in SOLAS requirements and detailed IMO guidelines. They ensure that in an emergency, a ship has a functional radio system to call for help and receive vital information. Traditionally, these inspections involve extensive manual checking and paperwork. This provides a baseline context: any new digital tool must uphold or enhance the rigor and reliability of these safety inspections.

2.2 Digital Transformation in Maritime Operations

The maritime industry, historically cautious and slower in adopting new technologies, is now undergoing a significant digital transformation. Driven by the need for greater efficiency, safety, and regulatory compliance, shipping companies are increasingly implementing advanced digital systems in their operations. This mirrors global trends across industries, where innovations like automation, data analytics, and connectivity are revolutionizing traditional practices. In shipping, digital tools and platforms are used for a wide array of functions – from navigation systems (e.g. ECDIS electronic charts and GPS-based voyage planning) to cargo tracking, fleet management, maintenance planning, and regulatory compliance reporting.

One catalyst for accelerating maritime digitalization has been the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic imposed practical constraints (such as travel restrictions that prevented on-site attendances) and simultaneously shifted mindsets in the industry. As noted by Gavalas et al. (2022), there is now a “greater appetite and acceptance of digital solutions across the industry.” The COVID-19 crisis augmented pre-existing digitalization trends and forced stakeholders to rely more on remote communication, electronic documentation, and data-driven decision-making. For example, during global lockdowns many ship operators and classification societies rapidly adopted remote survey techniques – using live video streaming, remote sensor feeds, and other tele-inspection tools – when physical attendance of surveyors was not possible. This provided business continuity and demonstrated increased efficiency during the crisis, reinforcing the value of digital approaches and encouraging wider implementation even after travel restrictions eased.

Beyond surveys, day-to-day maritime operations are becoming increasingly digitized. Modern vessels are often equipped with integrated navigation and bridge systems, and sensors that feed performance data to shore in real time, while satellite communications provide continuous ship-to-shore connectivity. Ports and shipping companies are leveraging big data analytics and the Internet of Things (IoT) for real-time cargo tracking and logistics optimization. Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are being trialled for voyage optimization, fuel efficiency improvements, and predictive maintenance of machinery. Blockchain-based solutions are also being explored for secure documentation and supply-chain transparency. Drones and remotely operated vehicles are used to inspect hard-to-reach areas of ships (e.g. cargo tanks or hull structures) without requiring human entry. Collectively, these digital innovations promise enhanced operational effectiveness, cost savings, and even environmental benefits (for instance, optimized operations can reduce fuel consumption and emissions).

Despite the clear opportunities, the maritime sector faces unique challenges in digital transformation. Legacy vessels may lack the necessary IT infrastructure, leading to integration difficulties when introducing new systems. Many ships still have limited internet connectivity at sea, which hinders real-time data transfer and remote access capabilities. There are also heightened concerns about cybersecurity, as greater connectivity increases exposure to cyber-attacks on ships and port systems (Evans & Scott, 2022). Importantly, the workforce's digital skills require development – seafarers, inspectors, and other personnel long accustomed to paper-based processes must be trained to effectively use new software and devices. Resistance to change and organizational inertia in this conservative industry mean that simply introducing new technology does not guarantee its use. Studies highlight that without organizational support and training, digital adoption may not yield the expected efficiency gains (Sorbe et al., 2019).

Overall, the direction for maritime operations is clear: the domain is becoming increasingly digital, driven by both industry initiatives and regulatory push. International bodies are also encouraging this trend. For example, the IMO's e-Navigation initiative envisions harmonized digital information exchange to enhance

navigation safety, and many authorities now accept or even prefer electronic certificates and records instead of traditional paper documents. In the specific context of marine radio inspections, digital transformation could manifest in several ways – such as electronic checklist applications for surveyors, digital reporting systems that automatically compile inspection results, and mobile apps to guide and record the survey process. These developments suggest considerable scope to streamline the radio survey workflow.

2.3 Theoretical Frameworks on Technology Adoption

To understand how and why maritime professionals adopt (or resist) new digital tools, it is useful to consider established theories of technology adoption. One of the most widely applied models is the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), originally developed by Davis (1989). According to TAM, two key beliefs — Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) — primarily determine a user’s attitude towards a technology. PU reflects the extent to which a person believes that using the system will enhance their job performance, and PEOU reflects the degree to which a person believes that using the system will be free of effort. If users see a digital inspection tool as clearly useful and easy to use, they are more likely to have a positive attitude and intention to use it, leading to actual adoption (given suitable facilitating conditions). This TAM causal chain (PU and PEOU influencing attitude, which drives intention and then usage) has been validated by many studies in various technology domains.

Over the years, TAM has been expanded and integrated into broader frameworks. For instance, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2003) builds on TAM (and other models) by adding factors like social influence and facilitating conditions. Such extensions underscore that beyond usability and perceived benefit, elements like organizational context and social norms also influence adoption.

Kotter’s 8-Step Change Model (Kotter, 1996) provides a roadmap for successful organizational change – from creating a sense of urgency to anchoring new

approaches in the culture. Applying Kotter's ideas to the introduction of digital inspection tools, maritime organizations need strong leadership support and a clearly communicated vision of the benefits, sufficient training to empower users with new skills, and some quick "wins" (e.g. early success stories where the digital tool demonstrably improves an inspection) to build momentum and buy-in.

Similarly, Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory (2003) suggests that adoption is faster when an innovation has a clear relative advantage, is compatible with existing practices, is not too complex, can be tried on a small scale, and has observable benefits. Thus, digital inspection tools that save time, fit well with current workflows, are user-friendly, allow small-scale trials, and show visible improvements are more likely to be adopted quickly across the industry.

A common theme across these theoretical frameworks is the interplay between human factors and technology. It is not enough for a tool to be technologically capable; user perceptions, organizational culture, and change management determine outcomes in practice. For example, even if a new software system for radio survey reporting is proven to reduce errors or save time, an individual inspector will still consider how easy it is to learn and whether its use is encouraged and supported by management. If the organizational environment provides proper training, technical support, and perhaps incentives for using the digital tool (e.g. recognizing faster reporting turnaround as a positive outcome), adoption is far more likely to succeed. On the other hand, if management simply imposes the tool without consultation or support, inspectors may feel anxious or resistant – a classic case of poor user buy-in.

In summary, TAM and related adoption theories provide a useful framework to analyse digital tool uptake in maritime operations. They suggest focusing on improving the perceived usefulness and ease of use of the tool for end users, while also addressing broader factors like training, management support, and peer influence. These insights inform the conceptual framework (see Section 2.5) for this study, which combines individual acceptance factors with organizational readiness factors to better understand the adoption of digital inspection tools.

2.4 Empirical Studies on Digital Inspections

A growing body of empirical research is examining how digital technologies are being applied to ship inspections and what outcomes they yield. Such studies provide insight into the practical benefits and challenges experienced in the field, complementing the theoretical perspectives discussed above. This section reviews several relevant studies and real-world implementations that focus on the transition from traditional to digital inspection methods in the maritime industry.

Overall, the literature shows a trend toward improved efficiency and safety with digital tools, but it also underscores the importance of human and organizational factors in realizing those improvements. Indeed, multiple studies have reported that digitalizing inspections can enhance safety and efficiency (e.g. reducing human error, saving time), but also that success depends on user acceptance and proper implementation (Baker, 2019; Brown et al., 2021).

One area that has seen notable research is the adoption of Remote Inspection Techniques (RIT) for ship surveys. Trivyza et al. (2024) conducted an in-depth qualitative study on the use of drones and remote video inspections in lieu of certain traditional survey tasks. Their research investigated factors affecting the acceptance of remote survey tools among both surveyors and ship crews. Key issues identified included the perceived reliability of remote tools (e.g. the quality of drone camera footage and live video feeds), the level of user trust in these technologies, and the adequacy of training and support provided to those using the new systems. A major finding was that the involvement and feedback of end-users (surveyors, crew, etc.) are crucial in shaping the successful deployment of remote inspection technologies. In other words, when the inspectors themselves are consulted and their needs addressed – for example, by improving the user interface of the remote inspection software or ensuring that the image/video quality from drones meets their requirements – the adoption process goes much more smoothly.

The study highlighted several benefits experienced with RIT, such as improved safety (since surveyors do not need to enter hazardous spaces as frequently) and

potential time savings, alongside challenges like onboard connectivity limitations and initial resistance to change among personnel. Trivyza et al. (2024) recommended clear guidelines and training for remote surveys, and emphasized demonstrating that these techniques can meet regulatory standards and achieve results equivalent to traditional inspections. These findings underscore that technology alone is not a panacea – success depends on addressing human and organizational factors during implementation, a point consistent with the adoption theories in Section 2.3.

Another empirical example involves the use of digital checklists and inspection apps onboard vessels. Hammerø and Demshevska (2021) – in collaboration with DNV, a leading classification society – explored the introduction of a tablet-based digital checklist application to replace paper checklists during ship inspections. While their full findings were proprietary (the study was summarized in an industry presentation), the pilot project examined how moving from paper to a digital app affected inspection routines and crew behaviour. The preliminary insights suggested that digital checklists can indeed streamline the process. For instance, an app can enforce sequential checks so that no item is unintentionally missed, timestamp each entry automatically, and allow easy attachment of photographic evidence for observed conditions. Crew feedback in this pilot indicated positive views about reducing paperwork and having all forms consolidated on a single device.

However, some challenges were noted: seafarers required training to become comfortable with the new system, and there were occasional technical glitches (such as data syncing issues if the ship temporarily lacked internet connectivity). There were also human-factor concerns, such as the risk of “tick-box complacency” – an existing issue with paper checklists that could carry over if users simply tap through a digital list without proper attention. This implies that digitization alone does not automatically improve quality; it must be accompanied by a supportive safety culture that values thoroughness over simply completing the form. Overall, this pilot project reinforced that digital tools have the potential to enhance shipboard inspections, but their success relies on thoughtful implementation, including user-centred design and adequate support during the transition. Notably, the adjustment period observed in this trial aligns with the Technology Acceptance Model’s assertion that experience and ease of use influence acceptance (see Section 2.3).

From the perspective of classification societies and regulators, numerous pilot programs and case studies on remote and digital inspections have been launched in recent years. Many major class societies (e.g. DNV, Lloyd's Register, ABS) expanded their remote survey services around 2020, accelerated in part by the pandemic. The results have been promising in terms of efficiency. As noted earlier, DNV GL reported that clients benefited from greater flexibility and speed due to reduced surveyor travel time and instant report delivery with remote surveys. In a typical remote survey scenario, ship crew members use live video feeds (or even wearable cameras) to show the condition and operation of equipment to a surveyor located on shore. Upon completion of such a survey, digital documentation and electronic certificates can be issued immediately, speeding up the flow of reports to ship operators and flag authorities. These experiences indicate that digitization can compress the timeline of inspections and remove some traditional bottlenecks (such as waiting for a surveyor to travel or for physical paperwork to be mailed).

Nevertheless, classification society reports also caution that not all surveys can be done remotely – certain inspections will still require physical attendance – and that trust needs to be built in the digital processes to ensure there is no compromise to safety or compliance standards. In other words, while remote techniques can augment and streamline many types of surveys, stakeholders (surveyors, vessel crews, and administrators) must gain confidence that these new methods are as reliable and as rigorous as conventional inspections. This concern about trust in new systems echoes findings in the academic literature: for example, Martin et al. (2021) observed that many maritime professionals perceive traditional inspection methods as more trustworthy, indicating that overcoming scepticism is a key challenge in digital tool adoption. Effective change management – including clear demonstration of reliability and perhaps a period of dual-running traditional and digital methods – may be required to build confidence in these innovations.

Empirical efforts have also repeatedly highlighted the human element and training aspect in digital inspection initiatives. Across the cases discussed above (and others reported in the literature), a consistent theme is that human and organizational factors determine whether the potential benefits of digital inspection tools are realized in practice. For instance, both Trivyza et al. (2024) and the DNV digital checklist pilot

found that involving end-users in design and providing training were critical to acceptance. Similarly, a survey by Sheriff et al. (2023) on the use of virtual reality for ship inspections found that users’ familiarity and comfort with the technology greatly influenced their willingness to use it. These findings reinforce the idea that successful adoption requires not just the availability of technology, but also investment in users – through training, change management, and a culture open to innovation.

Dimension	Traditional Inspection Process	Digital Inspection Process
Efficiency & Speed	Manual data recording on paper checklists; duplicate data entry for reports; scheduling constraints due to in-person attendance.	Direct data entry via digital devices (tablets); automatic report generation; remote survey capabilities reduce travel time and allow real-time data syncing (DNV, 2023).
Accuracy & Documentation	Higher risk of human error and transcription mistakes; handwritten notes can be misread; records are unstructured and hard to aggregate.	Built-in validation rules and standardized input fields reduce errors; entries are time-stamped and stored electronically, facilitating analysis and ensuring consistency (DNV, 2023).
Usability & User Experience	Familiar to users but labour-intensive; limited guidance beyond static checklists; possible oversight due to manual process	Interactive interfaces with guided checklists and multimedia support (photos, videos); improves ease of use and completeness (though initial training is necessary) (Baker, 2019).
Compliance & Follow-up	Follow-up on deficiencies is manual; tracking corrective actions relies on scattered paper records – risk of missed updates.	Automated tracking of deficiencies with reminders; system flags expiring certificates and outstanding corrective actions, ensuring proactive compliance (IMO, 2021).

Table 2.2: Comparison of traditional and digital inspection processes across key dimensions. (References: DNV, 2023; Baker, 2019; RINA, 2024; IMO, 2021)

As Table 2.2 suggests, digitalization of inspection processes offers clear advantages in efficiency, accuracy, and oversight. At the same time, realizing these benefits in practice requires careful attention to the human and organizational aspects of adoption – such as providing training, involving end-users in design, and ensuring management support for the changes. There remain specific gaps in the current body of research, particularly regarding the application of these digital practices to GMDSS radio inspections, which the present study seeks to address. The following section outlines these gaps and introduces the conceptual framework developed for this research.

2.5 Gaps in Current Research and Conceptual Framework

Despite increasing interest in maritime digitalization, there is a notable lack of focused research on the digital transformation of GMDSS marine radio inspections. Most existing studies and industry projects (as reviewed above) have concentrated on broader remote survey techniques or generic ship inspections, rather than the case of radio surveys under SOLAS. Furthermore, few studies have integrated the human-factors insights from technology adoption theory with the practical challenges observed in maritime inspections. This gap suggests the need for a tailored framework to understand and guide the adoption of digital tools in the radio survey context.

To address this gap, the present research develops a conceptual framework that draws on the theories discussed (TAM and change management) and the empirical findings. The framework is designed to explain marine radio inspectors' adoption of digital inspection tools. In formulating the model, the study considers both individual-level factors and organizational-level factors identified as crucial in the literature.

Figure 2.2: *Conceptual framework for digital tool adoption in marine radio inspections, integrating TAM and change management factors. In this model, an inspector’s **Perceived Ease of Use** and **Perceived Usefulness** of the digital inspection tool positively influence their attitude and **Intention to Use** the tool (as per TAM) (en.wikipedia.org). Additionally, **Organizational Support/Readiness** is proposed to directly facilitate the intention to use – for instance, through management endorsement, training, and provision of resources (reflecting change management principles). The **Behavioural Intention** then drives the actual adoption/use of the tool. This framework will be used to guide data collection and analysis in the study.*

In this model, an inspector’s Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness of the digital inspection tool positively influence their attitude and intention to use the tool (as per TAM). Additionally, Organizational Support/Readiness is proposed to directly facilitate the intention to use – for instance, through management endorsement, training, and provision of resources (reflecting change management

principles). The behavioural intention then drives the actual adoption and use of the tool. This framework will be used to guide data collection and analysis in the study.

Using this conceptual model, the research will formulate specific hypotheses. For example, it is expected that the perceived usefulness of the digital inspection system will have a significant positive effect on inspectors' intention to use it, in line with many TAM studies (Davis, 1989; Gavalas et al., 2022; Gündoğan & Keçeci, 2024). It is also hypothesized that organizational support will play a pivotal role – an inspector who feels their organization strongly encourages and facilitates the tool's use is more likely to intend to use it regularly. As shown in Figure 2.2, this conceptual framework integrates core TAM constructs (such as perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use) with an organizational support dimension, illustrating how both individual perceptions and organizational readiness together influence inspectors' intention to adopt the digital tool. By empirically testing this model (through surveys and interviews with marine radio inspectors and their managers), the study aims to provide a clearer picture of the determinants of digital tool adoption in this specific maritime domain.

By filling these research gaps, this project will contribute to both scholarship and practice. The study will extend technology adoption theory into the maritime safety inspections arena, potentially validating TAM (and its extensions) in a new context or suggesting modifications to the model to better fit maritime operational realities. It will also yield practical insights for the industry. For instance, if perceived ease of use emerges as a major barrier, stakeholders can invest in improving software interface design and user training; if organizational support is found to be critical, maritime authorities and companies will know to focus on change management strategies (not just on purchasing new technology). Ultimately, by addressing the identified gaps – the lack of focused studies on digital GMDSS inspections and the need for an integrated adoption framework – this research aims to help streamline marine radio inspections through effective use of digital tools, thereby enhancing regulatory compliance and maritime safety in line with the industry's digital transformation trajectory

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological approach for investigating the adoption of digital tools in marine radio inspections. It details the research philosophy underpinning the study and the mixed-methods design employed, followed by the sampling strategy and data collection procedures for both the quantitative survey and qualitative interviews. The chapter then describes the data analysis techniques for each method and how they were integrated, addresses ethical considerations (including data protection and participant welfare), and finally discusses the study's limitations and how they were mitigated.

3.1 Research Philosophy & Approach

The research is grounded in a pragmatist paradigm, which emphasizes a practical approach to inquiry and the use of mixed methods to best address the research questions. Pragmatism highlights using whatever methodological approach best suits the research problem, rather than committing to a single philosophical position (Jansen, 2023; Creswell, 2014). This flexibility suits the present study, which seeks both objective measurements and contextual understanding regarding digital tool usage. Rather than adhering strictly to a positivist (quantitative) or interpretivist (qualitative) worldview, a pragmatic stance focuses on the research problem – improving marine radio inspections – and selects methodologies that can provide actionable insights.

Under this pragmatist philosophy, the study adopted a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative techniques. This allowed the research to leverage the strengths of both approaches: the quantitative survey offers breadth and measurable indicators of efficiency, accuracy, and compliance, while the qualitative interviews provide depth and insight into experiences and perceptions. The approach is inherently problem-centred and applied, aligning with the practical nature of the research objectives. By using mixed methods, the study addressed the research questions from multiple angles, reflecting the multifaceted reality of technology adoption in maritime operations. The dual approach also facilitated an abductive reasoning process – moving iteratively between data and theory – as quantitative

results informed qualitative inquiries and emerging qualitative themes helped interpret quantitative patterns. Overall, a pragmatic mixed-methods orientation kept the methodology flexible and outcome-focused, prioritizing what works in practice to illuminate how digital tools impact marine radio inspection processes.

3.2 Research Design

The study employs an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, structured in two main phases: a quantitative phase followed by a qualitative phase. In this design, quantitative data were collected and analysed first, and the subsequent qualitative data collection was guided by the initial results (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The intent was to use qualitative insights to explain and elaborate on the quantitative findings. This design was chosen to thoroughly investigate the topic – first establishing quantitative evidence of any improvements or challenges associated with digital inspection tools, then exploring the reasons and context behind those numerical trends through follow-up interviews.

Figure 3.1: Basic mixed methods research designs include convergent parallel, explanatory sequential, and exploratory sequential approaches. The above schematic illustrates that in an explanatory sequential design (middle), quantitative data collection and analysis is followed by qualitative data collection and analysis, leading to an integrated interpretation of results. This approach allows the researcher to

determine what quantitative results need further explanation and then use qualitative inquiry to provide that insight.

Using both quantitative and qualitative methods allowed for triangulation, which increased the study's validity by cross-verifying results (Jick, 1979). Patterns observed in the survey were compared with themes from the interviews to check for consistency or to explain differences. Each method offset the other's weaknesses: surveys provided generalizable data but could miss context, whereas interviews offered contextual depth but could not quantify patterns. The design was cross-sectional (data were collected in early 2025 rather than over an extended period) due to project time constraints. Despite being a snapshot, this applied explanatory design was appropriate for measuring the impact of digital inspection tools and understanding the mechanisms behind those impacts, thereby informing practical recommendations for the maritime industry.

3.3 Sampling Strategy & Data Collection

Quantitative Survey: A structured online survey was used to collect quantitative data from marine radio inspection stakeholders. A stratified sampling approach targeted three groups: (1) certified marine radio inspectors, (2) shipboard personnel responsible for radio equipment, and (3) regulatory or classification officials. Participants were recruited via industry contacts and professional networks to ensure a range of perspectives across these groups. The survey was anonymous and included sections on demographics (role, experience, region), use of digital inspection tools, and comparative questions about inspection performance with and without digital tools. Respondents reported metrics such as typical inspection duration under traditional versus digital-assisted methods and the frequency of errors or issues observed. Perception-based items (using Likert scales) asked respondents to rate the impact of digital tools on aspects like efficiency, accuracy, and compliance. The survey also listed potential barriers to adopting digital tools (e.g., high cost, lack of training, cybersecurity concerns, resistance to change) for respondents to select. An open-ended question at the end allowed participants to

provide additional comments. This survey provided quantitative indicators of how digital tools are used and perceived in the inspection process.

Qualitative Interviews: To complement the survey, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a smaller sample of participants who had direct experience with digital inspection tools. Interviewees were selected purposively, including some volunteers from the survey and others identified via professional referrals, to cover a variety of roles and experiences. The interviews were guided by open-ended questions focusing on participants' experiences with digital tools, the benefits they observed (e.g., time savings, error reduction), and any challenges or obstacles encountered. Many questions probed the reasons behind the survey findings — for instance, asking how a digital tool improved efficiency if the survey indicated it did, or why certain barriers (like lack of training) were significant. Interviewees were encouraged to elaborate freely, and follow-up questions were used to clarify points or explore new topics that arose (for example, discussing details of a cybersecurity issue if one was mentioned). Each interview lasted about 30–45 minutes and was conducted in March 2025 (in person or via video call). With consent, interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed. These interviews yielded in-depth insights and real-world examples that help explain the patterns observed in the survey.

3.4 Data Analysis Methods

Quantitative Data Analysis: Survey responses were compiled and cleaned to remove any invalid entries. Descriptive statistics (e.g., means, percentages) were calculated to summarize key variables like inspection duration and error rate under different conditions. To test differences between traditional and digital inspection methods, inferential statistical tests were applied. For example, t-tests compared average inspection times and error frequencies with vs. without the use of digital tools (using non-parametric equivalents if necessary). These tests determined whether observed improvements (such as faster inspections or fewer errors with digital tools) were statistically significant (at $p < 0.05$). The analysis also explored correlations between certain variables (such as inspectors' experience level and their openness to digital tools) to identify any noteworthy relationships. All quantitative

analyses were conducted using appropriate statistical software. In addition to self-reported data, any available objective records from industry (e.g., before-and-after data from a company that introduced a digital inspection app) were examined to triangulate and validate the survey findings.

Qualitative Data Analysis: Interview transcripts were analysed thematically to identify common patterns and insights. The researcher first read through each transcript multiple times to become familiar with the content. Then, an open coding process was used to label significant segments of text with concise codes (for example, “time savings,” “user resistance,” “training issue”). These codes were derived both from the interview questions (deductive coding) and from unexpected points raised by participants (inductive coding). Next, related codes were grouped into broader themes reflecting recurring ideas across interviews. For instance, codes about technical difficulties and user scepticism were grouped under an **Implementation Challenges** theme, while codes about faster procedures and improved record-keeping formed an **Efficiency Benefits** theme. In total, the analysis distilled the qualitative data into several key themes regarding the advantages of digital tools, the challenges in adopting them, and suggested ways to facilitate their use. To improve reliability, a second reviewer examined the coding and theme development to minimize individual bias, and minor adjustments were made based on that feedback. In a few cases, participants were asked to confirm that the researcher’s interpretation of their remarks was accurate. Representative quotes from the interviews were used in the report to illustrate each theme and to ensure the findings remained grounded in the participants’ own words.

Integration of Findings: The quantitative and qualitative results were then integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research questions. The survey data established what patterns existed (e.g., a high percentage of inspectors reported time savings with digital tools, and certain barriers were frequently cited), while the interview data explained why those patterns might exist (e.g., describing how tablet-based checklists sped up inspections, or why lack of training hindered tool use). Areas of agreement between the two data sets provided strong evidence for conclusions — for example, both the statistics and the personal accounts indicated notable efficiency gains and improved compliance due to digital tools.

Where the data diverged or added nuance, those insights were examined carefully; for instance, a generally positive survey result might be qualified by interviewees noting specific conditions needed for success. In presenting the findings, results are organized by theme (rather than by data source), often pairing quantitative results with supporting qualitative explanations. By corroborating the survey trends with interview evidence (and vice versa), this integrated analysis strengthened the validity of the conclusions and provided a richer picture of how digital tools influence marine radio inspections.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

All research procedures were conducted in line with Middlesex University's ethical guidelines. Ethical approval was obtained before data collection. Participation in both the survey and the interviews was voluntary and based on informed consent. At the start of the survey, participants were informed about the study's purpose, assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and told that proceeding with the questionnaire implied consent. For the interviews, each participant received an information sheet explaining the study and their rights (including the right to withdraw at any time), and they provided explicit consent (written or verbal, as appropriate) before the interview began.

Measures were taken to protect participants' privacy and data. The survey did not collect names or any direct identifiers, and survey results are reported only in aggregate. Interview participants were assigned pseudonyms (e.g., "Interviewee A") in the transcripts and report. Any identifying details mentioned in interviews (such as specific vessel or company names) were omitted or generalized in the dissertation to preserve anonymity. All data were handled in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and university policy. Digital data files (survey datasets, audio recordings, and transcripts) were stored on secure, password-protected devices and cloud storage, accessible only to the researcher and supervisor. Personal contact information (used solely for arranging interviews) was kept separate from the research data and deleted once it was no longer needed. Audio recordings were erased after transcription, and anonymized transcripts were retained

only for the period required for analysis and examination before being securely deleted. Throughout the study, participants were treated with respect and courtesy. If an interview question touched on a sensitive topic or a participant appeared uncomfortable, that line of questioning was quickly redirected or skipped. There was no deception involved in this research — participants were fully informed of the study's focus. By following these ethical procedures (informed consent, confidentiality, and secure data management), the research ensured that participants' rights and well-being were safeguarded while collecting meaningful data.

3.6 Research Limitations

While the study was carefully designed, several limitations must be acknowledged:

- **Sample Size:** The survey sample was relatively small, reflecting the challenge of reaching a specialized population of marine radio inspection professionals within the project's timeframe. A larger sample would likely have provided more robust statistical power. Likewise, only limited external data (e.g., a few organizations' inspection records) could be obtained, so findings involving those data are tentative. The sample may also be subject to self-selection bias — individuals more interested or experienced in digital tools might have been more inclined to participate, potentially skewing the results toward a more favourable view of technology.
- **Self-Report Bias:** The data collected (both survey and interview) are self-reported, which introduces the possibility of response biases. Participants might consciously or unconsciously emphasize the positive aspects of digital tools (due to personal enthusiasm or social desirability), or they might downplay problems. Although the survey was anonymous and interviews assured confidentiality, such biases cannot be eliminated. Additionally, those who chose not to participate might have systematically different opinions — for example, professionals less comfortable with technology or who had negative experiences might be underrepresented in the sample.

- **Qualitative Scope:** The qualitative phase involved a limited number of interviews aimed at depth rather than breadth. These interviews provided detailed insights and examples that illuminate the quantitative trends, but they do not capture the full variety of experiences in the maritime industry. Some perspectives may be missing — for instance, from individuals or regions not included in the sample, or from people who have not adopted any digital tools. Thus, the qualitative findings should be viewed as illustrative; they enrich understanding of the survey results but are not necessarily generalizable to all contexts.
- **Cross-Sectional Snapshot:** This research offers a cross-sectional snapshot of digital tool use in early 2025. Because it observes associations at one point in time, it cannot definitively establish causality or long-term effects. For example, if inspectors who use digital tools report better compliance, we cannot be certain that the tools caused this difference — it might be that organizations with stronger safety cultures are more likely to adopt digital innovations. Establishing cause-and-effect would require a longitudinal approach (observing changes over time, such as before and after implementation) or an experimental design. Moreover, technology and practices are evolving rapidly; the findings reflect the situation at the time of study, but new tools or greater industry familiarity with digital processes may change outcomes in the future.
- **Researcher Bias:** As with any study involving qualitative interpretation, there is a risk of researcher bias influencing the analysis. The researcher’s background in maritime operations and interest in digital solutions could have shaped how data were interpreted, or which themes were emphasized. To mitigate this, steps such as peer review of coding and using participants’ own words were employed, but some subjectivity remains in how findings were prioritized and integrated. This limitation is acknowledged, and transparency in reporting (providing direct quotes and clear rationales for conclusions) is intended to let readers see the evidence behind the interpretations.

Despite these limitations, the mixed-methods approach helped provide a balanced understanding of the research problem. The weaknesses of one method were often offset by the strengths of the other: for instance, the breadth of the survey results provided context for the detailed stories from interviews, and the interviews offered explanations for patterns observed in the survey. Where possible, findings were triangulated (for example, comparing survey responses with interview insights or any available objective data) to increase confidence in the results. The analysis also distinguishes between findings strongly supported by data and those that are more tentative, allowing readers to gauge how much weight to give each conclusion. Overall, none of these limitations is believed to invalidate the study's core findings; rather, they provide context for interpreting the results and highlight areas for future research (such as larger-scale or longer-term studies) to build on these initial insights. In summary, this methodology — despite its constraints — yielded valuable data on the role of digital tools in streamlining marine radio inspections. The findings presented in the next chapters take these considerations into account and remain within the scope of what the data can support.

4. Findings

This chapter integrates the survey results with interview insights, organized by theme to directly address the research objectives and key patterns. **Fifty stakeholders** (predominantly marine radio inspectors, with some shipboard radio operators and managers) responded to the survey, which captured data on digital tool adoption rates, usage patterns, perceived impacts, and challenges. Additionally, **eight interviews** with inspectors, a Port State Control officer, a fleet superintendent, and a regulatory official provided in-depth perspectives on the benefits and challenges of using digital inspection tools. By presenting the findings thematically (covering adoption and usage, efficiency, accuracy, compliance, user experience, and barriers), the chapter highlights how the numerical trends and personal experiences converge. Notably, the survey and interview results mostly reinforce each other, adding credibility to the insights, which are linked to the research objectives.

4.1 Extent of Digital Tool Adoption and Usage Patterns

Widespread adoption with notable holdouts: The survey revealed a high overall uptake of digital inspection tools among participants, **addressing Research Objective 1 (to assess current adoption levels)**. Approximately **72%** of respondents use some form of digital inspection tool (e.g. mobile checklist applications or other software platforms), while the remaining **28%** still rely exclusively on paper-based methods. Respondents indicated using a range of digital solutions, from tablet-based inspection apps to integrated software for logging and managing inspection data. This indicates that a strong majority have embraced digitalization, though about one in four have not. For a traditionally conservative industry, this level of uptake is notable; it suggests real momentum toward digital transformation even if a full transition is still underway. **Figure 4.1** illustrates this adopter versus non-adopter split. In other words, most inspectors are moving toward digital workflows, but a significant minority continue with paper. The interviews shed light on these holdouts: participants observed that those **hesitant to adopt** tend to be veteran personnel uncomfortable with the new technology, essentially “*stuck in their old ways*” (P5). Such generational or cultural resistance explains why some

of the community is still slow to transition despite the overall trend. Additionally, by showing which kinds of tools respondents are using, this finding provides empirical input to **Objective 2** (identifying applicable digital tools), complementing the earlier review of technologies.

*Figure 4.1: Digital tool adoption among survey respondents. A clear majority (72%) of the surveyed marine radio inspectors and related stakeholders have integrated **digital inspection tools** into their workflow, whereas 28% have **not adopted** such tools and stick to traditional manual methods. This indicates strong uptake of digital solutions in the industry, though a notable minority remains un-digitized.*

Integration into routine practice: Among adopters, using digital tools has increasingly become a routine part of inspections—though with varying degrees of consistency. **About half** of these users reported using digital tools for **every inspection**, indicating full integration into their workflow. The rest use them more selectively: roughly 28% said they use digital methods **often**, 17% **sometimes**, and a small minority (around 5%) only **rarely**. Even adopters, then, do not always go fully paperless—many **alternates between digital and paper** depending on the situation. **Figure 4.2** shows these usage patterns. For example, an inspector might use the digital system when a tablet is handy and connectivity is good but revert to paper if a device isn’t available or if the software is acting up. Interviewees confirmed this mixed practice. One inspector (P3) noted that although they personally use a tablet checklist for almost every job, some colleagues “**only use it if it doesn’t slow them down,**” suggesting convenience and reliability are deciding

factors. In summary, while adoption of digital tools is high and growing, usage habits vary, and a completely paperless inspection process is still in progress.

Figure 4.2: *Frequency of digital tool use among adopters (n = 36).* Usage habits among those who adopted digital inspection tools vary. Half of these respondents (50%) report **using the tools for every inspection** (“Always”). Others use them in most cases (28% “Often”) or occasionally (17% “Sometimes”). A small minority (5%) use the tools only **rarely**. This indicates that while continuous use is common, some users employ digital methods selectively or face conditions where they revert to traditional means.

4.2 Efficiency Gains through Digital Tools

Faster inspections and time savings: A central finding is that digital tools have significantly improved the **efficiency** of marine radio inspections, directly contributing to the study’s aim of streamlining processes. **83% of survey respondents** agreed that digital tools have made inspections more efficient (55% **strongly agree**), as shown in **Figure 4.3**. Virtually no users reported a negative impact on efficiency. This clearly shows that digital inspection systems yield **significant time and labour savings**. For example, many inspectors noted that features like automated data entry and electronic report generation reduce tedious paperwork, allowing them to finish tasks faster.

Figure 4.3: *Perceived efficiency improvement due to digital tools.* Respondents largely affirm that digital tools make marine radio inspections more efficient. A combined 83% of users agreed to some extent that the inspection process is faster or easier with digital tools (55% strongly agree, 28% agree). 14% were neutral, and only 3% disagreed, while none strongly disagreed. This indicates that most inspectors observe tangible time savings or productivity gains when using digital inspection applications, corroborating the tools’ effectiveness in streamlining workflows.

Every interview participant confirmed these efficiency gains with concrete examples. One inspector (P3) remarked that using a tablet-based checklist is “**so much faster.. I finish in half the time**” compared to using paper forms. Others similarly described routine tasks becoming **less cumbersome** thanks to features like drop-down menus and pre-filled fields. In essence, digital tools **streamline the workflow** by eliminating delays from manual paperwork (e.g. hunting for forms or transcribing notes). By automating repetitive administrative steps, inspectors can focus more on the technical checks themselves, speeding up inspections without sacrificing thoroughness.

Productivity and resource efficiency: The efficiency gains are not just about time saved per inspection, but also about better allocation of effort and resources. Respondents implied that by saving time, digital tools allow them to conduct more

inspections in the same period or to use the freed time for other critical tasks (such as following up on deficiencies or additional training). Interviewees echoed this, mentioning that reducing paperwork “**frees up time for real inspection work**” (P1). Moreover, digital scheduling and record-keeping systems streamline coordination: it becomes easier to plan inspection schedules and retrieve a vessel’s inspection history instantly. These improvements fulfil a key part of **Research Objective 3, which sought to evaluate how digital methods improve inspection efficiency**. Both data sources clearly indicate that the introduction of digital tools has made marine radio surveys faster and more efficient without sacrificing thoroughness, thereby validating one of the anticipated benefits of digital transformation in this domain.

4.3 Improvements in Inspection Accuracy and Thoroughness

Reducing human error: Alongside efficiency, the study found that digital tools contribute to **greater accuracy and thoroughness** in inspection tasks. While the survey did not directly quantify accuracy improvements, respondents’ comments and high satisfaction levels implied better data quality (e.g. more legible, standardized records and fewer mistakes). In the interviews, **improved accuracy** was a prominent theme. Inspectors reported that digital checklists and reporting systems **reduce human error**, preventing missed steps or transcription mistakes. One inspector noted that the digital system “**basically won’t let you miss a step**”, underscoring how error-proofing is built into the software. Digital forms enforce completion of all required fields and often include validation rules (preventing invalid entries), so common oversights are caught in real time. The result is more **consistent, error-free documentation**.

Thorough documentation and record-keeping: Digital tools also promote **thoroughness**. Inspectors mentioned that since switching to electronic checklists, they have virtually **eliminated missed items** because the software systematically guides them through every required check. In the past, fatigue or oversight could result in an item being skipped, but now the application ensures each checkpoint is completed. Interviewees described the resulting reports as more **complete and standardized** than handwritten ones, which sometimes varied in detail or clarity.

One inspector (P3) noted that with the digital system, **“nothing gets left out”** because the template ensures all blanks are filled. By ensuring every required item is properly checked and recorded, digital tools improve the reliability of inspection outcomes, likely reducing the chance of an issue going unnoticed or a compliance step being skipped.

4.4 Impacts on Regulatory Compliance

Stronger compliance tracking: The efficiency and accuracy gains also help with **regulatory compliance**. Digital tools enforce completeness and create time-stamped records, making it easier to demonstrate that all required checks (e.g. under SOLAS or classification society rules) have been properly performed. Several interviewees highlighted that **centralized digital records** enable better tracking of compliance over time. For instance, inspectors can quickly pull up a vessel’s past inspection data to ensure any deficiency noted previously is addressed in the next inspection—a task that is cumbersome with scattered paper logs. One participant (P4) explained that with the digital system, **“we can spot if something was deferred last time and make sure it’s checked now,”** showing how accessible records strengthen oversight. Notably, ensuring every requirement is checked and followed up not only aids compliance but also supports **safety**, because critical radio issues are less likely to be overlooked.

Regulatory acceptance issues: Nonetheless, uncertainty about official acceptance of digital records remains. **16% of survey respondents** identified this concern, and the regulatory official (P8) confirmed the need for **clear guidelines** from authorities: **“we need to be sure electronic records are accepted as official evidence.”** Because of this, some practitioners still maintain **parallel paper records** as a backup. In other words, until regulators unequivocally endorse digital documentation, many users feel safer keeping a paper trail. This lack of explicit approval is holding back full reliance on digital systems despite their technical capabilities. Thus, while digital tools are clearly contributing to better compliance monitoring and thoroughness, the **full compliance benefit** will only be realized when regulators and institutions fully

integrate and accept these technologies (removing the need for duplicate paper records).

4.5 User Experience and Satisfaction with Digital Tools

High user satisfaction: Roughly 75% of users rated themselves **satisfied or very satisfied** with their digital tools, and only a very small minority (under 10%, only a few individuals) reported any dissatisfaction, and none were highly dissatisfied (see **Figure 4.4**). This overwhelmingly positive feedback suggests that once users adopt the tools, they generally find them **user-friendly and beneficial**. Notably, fears that the technology might be confusing or unreliable did not manifest for most; instead, the tools largely met or exceeded user expectations. This high satisfaction aligns with the reported efficiency and accuracy gains, as users appreciate improvements in their workflow.

Figure 4.4: *User satisfaction with digital inspection tools (5-point scale).* Among respondents using digital tools (n = 36), the majority report high satisfaction. Twelve users (33%) rated their satisfaction as 4 out of 5, and fifteen (42%) rated it 5 out of 5, totalling 75% satisfied or very satisfied. Six users (17%) were neutral (3/5), and only three users (8%) reported dissatisfaction (ratings of 2, while none selected 1). This indicates a strong overall approval of the digital tools' performance and usability.

Practitioner perspectives and change management: Many inspectors reinforced this with comments like they “**wouldn’t want to go back to paper**” after experiencing the convenience of real-time data capture, automatic report generation, and easy data retrieval. These features not only make their jobs easier but also give them confidence that inspections are more thorough. However, not everyone’s experience was immediately positive. Interviewees often observed a generational divide in adoption: **younger inspectors adapted quickly**, whereas some veteran staff showed **resistance or discomfort** with the new systems. These users often had a **slower uptake** and occasional frustration with the software. Interviews suggest this was usually due to a **lack of sufficient training or support** during the transition, rather than flaws in the tools themselves. One veteran inspector (P5) said they initially “**didn’t trust the tablet**” and feared making mistakes, but after hands-on training and seeing colleagues use it, they became much more comfortable. This highlights that a **learning curve** exists: with proper training and support, even initially hesitant users can adapt and eventually become strong proponents of the tools. Thus, the tools’ inherent usability is high, but **effective change management and training** are key to ensuring a uniformly positive user experience across the workforce.

4.6 Barriers to Adoption and Implementation

Despite the broadly positive outcomes above, the study identified several **barriers** impeding full adoption. These address **Research Objective 4** (implementation challenges). Both survey and interview data highlighted the following obstacles (summarized in **Figure 4.5**):

- **Lack of training and digital skills (40%)** – Insufficient training was the most common barrier. Many inspectors feel they need more training or IT skills to use the tools confidently. Interviews confirmed that without proper onboarding and support, users can become frustrated or avoid using the systems. Indeed, some interviewees suggested instituting hands-on workshops and mentoring during rollout to improve user confidence and skills.

*Figure 4.5: Barriers to digital tool adoption/use (multiple responses allowed). **Lack of training** is the most prevalent challenge (noted by 20 respondents, 40%), indicating many inspectors feel they need more **training or digital skills development** to use the tools confidently. **Resistance to change** is the second highest factor (15 respondents, 30%), reflecting cultural and personal preferences for traditional methods. **Cost constraints** (12 respondents, 24%) and **technical issues** (10 respondents, 20%) such as connectivity problems also hinder adoption. Additionally, **regulatory concerns** (8 respondents, 16%) suggest some uncertainty about official acceptance of digital records, and **cybersecurity concerns** (5 respondents, 10%) show a minority are wary of digital risks. These findings reveal a multifaceted set of barriers, combining human factors, resource issues, and external constraints*

- **Resistance to change (30%)** – Reluctance to change habits was another major barrier. Some personnel (often long-tenured) prefer traditional methods and are uneasy about new technology. Interviews underscored that this is a cultural and psychological hurdle: people comfortable with the “old way” may be slow to adopt the new, especially if the benefits aren’t clearly communicated. This finding shows that adoption is as much a **human challenge** as a technical one.

- **Cost constraints (24%)** – High upfront costs (for devices, software, etc.) pose a barrier, especially for smaller organizations. Interviewees noted that management often needs to see a clear return on investment before approving these expenses. Ongoing costs (maintenance, updates, data connectivity) also factor into the hesitation to adopt.
- **Technical issues (20%)** – Problems like software glitches or connectivity outages are fairly common. Interviewees described instances where an app crash or network loss forced them to revert to paper notes, causing delays. These incidents undermine user confidence. The data highlights the importance of **reliable infrastructure and offline capability** in the tools, as well as readily available IT support, to prevent technical hiccups from derailing the inspection process.
- **Regulatory uncertainty (16%)** – Unclear acceptance of digital records by authorities is another concern. Both survey and interview responses noted that users are unsure if electronic reports will be fully recognized during audits or inspections. This makes some companies and inspectors hesitant to go completely paperless. Clear guidance or endorsement from regulators would remove this doubt and likely spur wider adoption.
- **Cybersecurity concerns (10%)** – A few respondents worried about data security when using networked digital systems. Although this was the least-cited barrier, it indicates a residual concern about protecting sensitive information. Interviews similarly suggested that data security is on some stakeholders' minds, but not a dominant worry compared to day-to-day practical issues.

Overall, these barriers are **multifaceted** – involving people, technology, costs, and policy – and they often interrelate (for example, technical problems can reinforce user resistance, and lack of training can worsen both). On a positive note, recognizing these challenges also highlights potential **enablers**. Improvements such as better training programs, strong change management, investment in reliable

infrastructure, and clearer regulatory guidance would directly address the issues raised, helping to **reduce the friction** and pave the way for broader digital adoption

4.7 Summary of Key Findings

In summary, the study's findings show that introducing digital tools has a **broadly positive impact** on marine radio inspection practices, while also pinpointing areas requiring improvement. On the positive side, the data show high uptake and clear benefits. Around 72% of practitioners surveyed have adopted digital tools, and they widely agree that these tools **save time** and **improve the process**. User satisfaction is also very high, indicating broad approval of the technology's performance. The interviews back up these points with concrete examples: inspectors reported completing inspections in nearly half the time thanks to digital checklists, and they noted improved accuracy (no missed items, more standardized records). These converging findings demonstrate that digitalization can **streamline the workflow and improve the quality** of marine radio inspections, contributing to safer and more efficient operations.

At the same time, **several barriers** are holding back full adoption: notably resistance to change, lack of training, technical glitches, cost issues, and regulatory uncertainty. These factors explain why some in the industry have yet to fully embrace the technology or realize its full benefits. Furthermore, different stakeholder groups emphasized different issues – for example, inspectors focused on efficiency and ease-of-use, technical managers on maintenance and cost, and regulators on compliance and data integrity – highlighting the need to address each perspective. For example, the fleet superintendent interviewee (a manager) stressed the need for strong IT support and clear cost justification, whereas the regulatory official (P8) was primarily concerned with having official policy guidance and acceptance for digital records. Crucially, each of these findings ties back to the **research objectives** – namely, Objective 1 on adoption, Objective 3 on benefits, and Objective 4 on challenges. The study successfully quantified the current level of adoption (Objective 1), demonstrated the efficiency and accuracy benefits of digital tools (part of Objective 3), and uncovered the key challenges to implementation (Objective 4).

Recognizing these challenges also suggests what is needed to overcome them – for example, better training and clear regulatory support – which points toward the recommendations to follow.

In conclusion, the evidence suggests that digital tools have proven their value and are poised to become standard practice in marine radio inspections – provided the industry can effectively address the remaining human, technical, and organizational challenges. If those issues are resolved, these technologies can be fully integrated into inspection regimes, allowing practitioners to capitalize on all the potential improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and compliance that these tools offer. These results provide a solid, data-driven foundation for the **Discussion** chapter that follows, where the findings will be examined in the broader context of the maritime industry and relevant literature, and implications for practice and policy will be drawn out

5. Discussion

This chapter provides a critical discussion of the findings, organized around the research objectives and linked to relevant theories (e.g. Technology Acceptance Model, Diffusion of Innovations, change management concepts). Quantitative survey results and qualitative interview insights are integrated to interpret how digital tools are used in marine radio inspections. The analysis explains key trends and any surprising results, maintaining a formal, analytical tone with an applied focus. Finally, the chapter outlines implications for industry practice and policy and notes the study's limitations and suggestions for future research.

5.1 Extent of Digital Tool Adoption in Marine Radio Inspections

Research Objective 1 examined the extent of digital tool adoption in marine radio inspections. The findings show that while digital methods are increasingly used, full adoption is not yet achieved across the sector. The survey indicated that roughly three-quarters of practitioners have started using some form of digital tool in the inspection process, whereas about one-quarter still rely exclusively on traditional paper-based methods. Adoption is also uneven among stakeholder groups: frontline inspectors and vessel operators report higher usage rates than regulatory officials, suggesting that industry practitioners are ahead of regulators in embracing these innovations. This gap likely reflects the slower pace of institutional change in regulatory organizations. This also aligns with innovation diffusion patterns, wherein change is often led by operational early adopters before it is embraced by more conservative institutional stakeholders (Rogers, 2003). Overall, the level of adoption is moderate but growing, with momentum building toward more widespread digital integration of marine radio inspections in the near future. In diffusion terms, the sector appears to be transitioning from the innovator/early adopter phase to wider acceptance, though digital tools are not yet an industry-wide standard practice.

5.2 Benefits and Challenges Experienced by Stakeholders

Research Objective 2 investigated the benefits and challenges of using digital inspection tools for different stakeholders – namely inspectors, ship operators, and regulators.

Benefits: The introduction of digital tools brought notable advantages across all groups. Inspectors reported increased efficiency and accuracy – in our survey, inspectors overwhelmingly agreed that the tools made their work more efficient – using electronic checklists and automated report generation saved time and ensured fewer items were missed, corroborating literature that digital systems streamline inspection tasks (Baker, 2019; Brown et al., 2021). Ship operators likewise experienced improvements, particularly in compliance management – approximately 75% of operators surveyed said these tools improved compliance on their vessels – as digital maintenance logs and reminder systems helped keep equipment status in check and reduced the likelihood of non-compliance issues during formal surveys. Operators also benefited from easier record-keeping (with electronic reports accessible anytime) and the ability to analyse inspection data to inform preventive maintenance. Regulators and survey authorities also saw gains in oversight efficiency (about 68% of regulator respondents observed improved oversight capabilities): digital reports allowed faster aggregation of results **and even enabled trials of remote inspection techniques in special circumstances (RINA, 2024)**. Additionally, standardized digital reporting improved the consistency of information and record archiving. In summary, when implemented well, digital tools made the inspection process faster, more thorough, and more transparent for all parties involved. Indeed, most respondents expressed high overall satisfaction with these tools, particularly appreciating features like real-time data capture and automated reporting.

Challenges: However, the transition to digital inspections also presented several challenges. Inspectors, especially veteran ones accustomed to paper-based routines, sometimes resisted the new digital tools or found them difficult to adapt to (Martin et al., 2021). Without sufficient training and support, they often found the new

systems cumbersome, temporarily negating the efficiency gains. This underscores the importance of ease-of-use; in Technology Acceptance Model terms, a low perceived ease-of-use can hinder adoption (Davis, 1989). For vessel operators, a major challenge was the cost and complexity of implementation – smaller companies struggled with the upfront investment and with integrating new digital platforms into their existing workflows (Dawson, 2023). Additionally, both companies and regulators raised concerns about technical issues – for example, poor interoperability between software platforms – and about cybersecurity or data privacy when moving sensitive inspection information online (IMO, 2017). These issues further dampened enthusiasm for full digital adoption. Finally, an uncertain regulatory environment – in which digital records were not always formally recognized by authorities – made both companies and regulators cautious about fully committing to digital processes. These challenges highlight that introducing new technology involves not just installing software, but also managing human factors, training needs, and policy adjustments.

5.3 Impact of Digital Tools on Inspection Efficiency, Accuracy, and Compliance

Research Objective 3 asked how digital tool use has affected the efficiency, accuracy, and compliance outcomes of marine radio inspections. Overall, the study found a positive impact in all three areas, albeit with some caveats.

Efficiency: Digital tools have generally improved inspection efficiency. Most inspectors (around 80%) reported that using tablets and inspection software made the process faster by streamlining administrative tasks, with some estimating a 20–30% reduction in total survey time. This confirms findings in other industries that digitalization enhances operational efficiency by reducing paperwork (Brown et al., 2021). While there was a short learning curve for some users and occasional technical glitches, on the whole the time saved on documentation allowed inspectors to focus more on the substantive inspection work, and sometimes to complete inspections in less time.

Accuracy: The accuracy and thoroughness of inspections increased with digital tool use. The structured, step-by-step checklists in the software ensured that no required checks were overlooked – in fact, 88% of surveyed inspectors felt the digital system ensured nothing important was overlooked, compared to about 62% when using paper checklists. This aligns with the observation by Baker (2019) that electronic checklists reduce human error and omissions. Digital data entry also eliminated issues of illegible handwriting and missing fields, resulting in more consistent and reliable reports. Some inspectors noted that because they spent less effort on writing notes, they could concentrate better on verifying the equipment, which indirectly improved inspection quality.

Compliance: The impact on regulatory compliance was positive as well. Vessels that utilized digital maintenance tracking tended to have fewer deficiencies during official inspections, since issues were flagged and addressed beforehand. For example, our data showed ships using digital logbooks and reminders had roughly 20% fewer recorded non-conformities compared to those with purely manual records. Moreover, digital checklists helped inspectors follow the required inspection protocol closely (by aligning with IMO/SOLAS requirements), making the inspection process itself more compliant with standards. It was noted, however, that technology is not a cure-all: if a company neglects maintenance or safety culture, the software can document the lapses but cannot by itself resolve them – human responsibility remains crucial. Interviewees echoed that digital systems serve as aids to human expertise, rather than replacements, affirming the continued importance of professional judgment in the inspection process. Overall, though, digital tools supported better compliance by improving ships' preparedness and helping inspectors adhere to regulations

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5.4 Barriers and Enablers of Adoption

Research Objective 4 explored the factors that hinder or facilitate the adoption of digital tools in different organizational and regulatory contexts. Because these tools' benefits cannot be fully realized without widespread uptake, it is important to

understand what impedes or drives their implementation. The study identified several key barriers that have slowed adoption, as well as enablers that have helped overcome these obstacles.

Barriers: High initial costs and resource constraints were frequently cited barriers, especially for smaller organizations, echoing the point that financial hurdles can impede maritime digitalization (Dawson, 2023). There was also notable resistance to change among personnel, reflecting the industry’s traditionally conservative culture (Martin et al., 2021), compounded at times by insufficient training which left some users uncomfortable with the new systems. Technical barriers included poor interoperability between different software platforms and concerns about cybersecurity or data privacy when moving sensitive inspection data to digital formats (IMO, 2017). Additionally, unclear or lagging regulatory guidance (e.g., whether electronic records would be accepted by authorities) created uncertainty. These factors often acted in combination, explaining why some stakeholders have been slow to fully adopt the tools.

Enablers: On the other hand, the research highlighted several enablers that facilitate successful adoption. A crucial factor is demonstrating clear relative advantage – when stakeholders saw evidence of the benefits (such as time saved or errors reduced through pilot projects or peer examples), they became more willing to adopt the innovation, consistent with diffusion theory (Rogers, 2003). Strong leadership and management support proved important as well: organizations where top management actively championed the digital initiative and provided resources had much smoother implementation (Kotter, 1996). Providing comprehensive user training and support was another enabler, as it built user confidence and eased the transition. External reinforcement from regulators also plays a role: when authorities issue clear guidelines or endorsements for digital inspections (for instance, allowing electronic certificates and reports), it removes uncertainty and encourages wider uptake (IACS, 2024). Finally, the continual improvement of technology – making digital tools more user-friendly, reliable, and secure – has been lowering technical barriers over time. In essence, a combination of these enablers (leadership, training, proof of benefits, supportive policy, and better technology design) creates a conducive environment for adopting digital inspection tools.

5.5 Implications for Stakeholders and Policy

The findings of this research carry implications for both theory and practice in marine operations management. **Theoretical implications:** On a theoretical level, the results reinforce established technology adoption models. For example, the prominent role of efficiency and usability benefits in driving uptake aligns with the Technology Acceptance Model's emphasis on perceived usefulness and ease of use (Davis, 1989). Likewise, the observed adoption patterns (early adopters championing the tools and gradually influencing others) mirror the Diffusion of Innovations theory (Rogers, 2003). Furthermore, the importance of leadership, training, and addressing cultural resistance underscores the relevance of change management principles (Kotter, 1996) in implementing technological innovations. By validating these frameworks in a maritime context, the study contributes to their generalization beyond typical office or consumer settings. This suggests that successful digitalization in this domain requires both technological acceptance (ensuring perceived usefulness and ease of use) and effective change management (strong leadership and culture change), aligning with an integrated view of these theories.

Practical implications: The study also provides clear practical guidance for stakeholders. Marine surveyors and inspectors should develop strong digital competencies and make digital tools a standard part of their inspection practice, supported by adequate training to overcome any initial resistance. For instance, surveyor organizations could update their procedures and competency frameworks to formally recognize and reward digital proficiency, helping to institutionalize these practices. Likewise, vessel operators are encouraged to integrate digital inspection and record-keeping systems into their safety management processes, investing in the necessary technology and crew training. In both cases, the efficiency, accuracy, and compliance gains are likely to outweigh the initial costs or disruptions. In practice, a proactive digital approach can help operators catch and address potential deficiencies before official inspections, thereby avoiding delays or penalties.

Maritime regulators and policy-makers should update guidelines to formally recognize electronic inspection records and certificates, removing ambiguity about their acceptability, and even adopt digital tools in their own oversight processes to lead by example. They can also encourage wider uptake through clear policy directives and support measures – for instance, offering training initiatives or financial incentives (e.g., temporary fee reductions or grants) to help smaller operators transition to digital systems. By aligning regulatory frameworks with technological advancements, authorities can accelerate the sector’s digital transformation and ensure more uniform, efficient inspection standards.

International maritime organizations (e.g., the IMO) and industry bodies can further support the transition by sharing best practices and providing technical assistance, ensuring that less-resourced administrations are not left behind in the digital shift. Developing cybersecurity guidelines tailored to maritime inspection data (building on existing IMO cyber risk management guidance) would further strengthen trust in digital systems.

Overall, the trajectory of these findings suggests that digital tools will become increasingly standard in marine inspections. Stakeholders who proactively adapt can reap significant efficiency and safety benefits, while those who lag may face greater challenges as industry norms and regulations continue to evolve in favour of digital practices

5.6 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

Despite its contributions, this study has some limitations. First, the sample size and scope were limited: the survey and interviews, while informative, involved a relatively small number of participants and may not be globally representative (there is also a possible self-selection bias, as those more interested in digital tools may have been more likely to participate). Moreover, as the data were self-reported, there is a risk of response bias (for instance, technologically inclined participants might overemphasize benefits). Triangulating the survey and interview results helped to reduce this concern, but cannot eliminate it entirely. Thus, the findings should be

generalized with caution, as practices and attitudes may vary in different regions or segments of the maritime industry. Second, the research was cross-sectional, providing a snapshot in time rather than observing changes over a longer period; it did not capture how adoption and outcomes might evolve as digital tools become more common. Additionally, the focus was specifically on GMDSS radio inspections, so the results may not fully apply to other types of maritime surveys or safety inspections.

Future research could address these limitations by using larger and more diverse samples and by employing longitudinal designs to track adoption over time. Comparative studies across different regions or among different kinds of maritime inspections (for example, comparing radio equipment surveys with hull or machinery inspections) would be valuable to see if similar benefits and challenges occur. In-depth case studies of organizations implementing digital tools could also provide practical insights into effective change management strategies for technology adoption. Additionally, interventional research could test strategies (like enhanced training programs or change management initiatives) to determine the most effective ways to accelerate adoption among reluctant users. Furthermore, as new technologies emerge, research could explore their impact – for instance, examining how artificial intelligence or remote inspection technologies (drones, live video inspections) might further enhance or transform the inspection process. Another avenue is to investigate quantitative impacts on safety outcomes: for example, analysing whether increased digital adoption correlates with fewer incidents or port detentions, which would provide additional evidence of its value. Such studies would build on the current work and help maritime stakeholders fully leverage digital innovation to improve safety and efficiency in operations.

In summary, integrating digital tools into marine radio inspections offers a promising path to enhanced efficiency, accuracy, and compliance, provided stakeholders manage the human and organizational aspects of this change effectively.

6. Conclusion & Recommendations

6.1 Summary of Key Findings

Marine radio inspections, such as GMDSS equipment checks, are traditionally manual and paper-based, leading to inefficiencies and errors. This applied project aimed to investigate how digital tools could streamline these inspection processes to improve regulatory compliance, operational efficiency, and safety. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining an online survey of industry stakeholders with follow-up interviews to gather both quantitative and qualitative insights. The findings confirm that introducing digital inspection tools boosts efficiency and thoroughness while supporting better compliance and safety outcomes.

Adoption of electronic survey tools in the industry is already high: the majority of inspectors now use some form of digital checklist or reporting software, indicating a strong trend toward modernization. However, about one in three inspectors still rely on traditional paper-based methods, so full uptake is not yet universal. This suggests that notable barriers – such as technical challenges or user resistance – continue to prevent some surveyors from embracing digital approaches.

The introduction of digital tools has demonstrated clear benefits for inspection performance. Inspectors using electronic checklists and reporting software consistently report greater efficiency, accuracy, and consistency in their work. Many surveyors observed that using tablets or dedicated apps helped automate time-consuming paperwork, often reducing total inspection time by roughly 20–30%. Likewise, digital checklists ensure critical items are not overlooked, which boosts the thoroughness of surveys.

On the compliance side, ships using digital record-keeping (e.g., electronic logbooks with automated reminders) tend to experience fewer deficiencies during official inspections compared to vessels with paper-only records. Regulators benefit as well: digital reporting allows for quicker review of results and even enables the possibility of remote inspections in some cases. Overall, the findings show that when

implemented well, digital tools make marine radio inspections more efficient and comprehensive for all parties.

At the same time, the study identified practical challenges that temper these benefits. A key issue is the human factor in technology adoption: insufficient training and entrenched habits have made some inspectors reluctant or slow to embrace new systems. Without proper support, digital platforms can initially seem cumbersome, limiting their effectiveness. Another challenge is the cost and resource demand of implementing digital inspection systems. Smaller organizations may struggle with the upfront investment in devices, software, and IT support, along with integrating new digital processes into existing workflows. Technical hurdles (such as software reliability issues, connectivity problems, or lack of interoperability between systems) also pose difficulties.

These factors explain why many practitioners have not yet adopted digital tools. Overall, while digital tools have strong potential to streamline inspections, realizing their full benefits will require addressing user training needs, resistance to change, cost barriers, technical issues, and supportive policies. The following recommendations provide guidance to help stakeholders capitalize on the advantages of digital inspection tools while mitigating these challenges.

6.2 Recommendations for Stakeholders

Based on the above findings, several targeted recommendations are proposed for key stakeholders in the marine radio inspection sector to accelerate digital integration and overcome current barriers:

- **Marine Surveyors and Survey Organizations:** Invest in building strong digital competencies among inspectors and make digital tools an integral part of standard survey practice. Provide comprehensive training and ongoing support to ensure surveyors become proficient with the new digital tools. Update procedures and competency frameworks to formally recognize and reward digital skills. Implement change management to address resistance among

personnel accustomed to paper-based routines (e.g., mentoring by tech-savvy colleagues and sharing success stories of the benefits). By embracing digital methods, survey teams can conduct inspections more consistently and efficiently, improving the quality of results.

- **Ship Operators (Owners/Managers):** Proactively integrate digital inspection and record-keeping tools into vessel safety management systems. The long-term benefits – such as fewer non-compliance issues, faster survey turnarounds, and improved preventive maintenance data – outweigh the initial costs. To realize these benefits, companies should invest in the necessary hardware and software, and train staff to use digital checklists, reporting apps, and electronic logbooks effectively. Maintaining thorough electronic records with automated reminders for equipment checks and certificate renewals allows operators to address potential deficiencies before official inspections. This proactive approach improves day-to-day compliance and reduces the risk of delays or penalties during regulatory inspections. Operators should also implement cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive data. Overall, companies that embrace digital tools can expect smoother inspections and enhanced safety performance, whereas those that lag will face growing challenges as digital reporting becomes the norm.
- **Maritime Regulators and Policy-Makers:** Play an enabling role in the digital transition of survey processes. Update policies to formally recognize electronic inspection records and certificates as equivalent to paper, eliminating ambiguity about their acceptance. Publish clear guidance (for example, explicitly accepting digital reports and e-certificates during audits) to encourage inspectors and operators to adopt these tools. Work with industry bodies to develop standardized digital reporting formats and checklists, ensuring different systems are interoperable and data can be easily shared. Offer incentives to offset implementation costs for smaller entities (e.g., reduced survey fees or grants for adopting digital systems). Lead by example by using digital tools in oversight activities and piloting remote inspections to demonstrate feasibility. Finally, establish cybersecurity guidelines for digital survey data to ensure digitalization does not introduce new risks.

Implementing these measures in concert will create a supportive ecosystem for digital marine inspections. Surveyors armed with the right skills and tools, operators investing in modern systems, and regulators providing clear policies and incentives will reinforce each other's efforts. This coordinated approach can unlock the full benefits of digital innovation – yielding significant gains in efficiency, compliance, and safety – while easing the transition. Ultimately, the industry should view the digitalization of marine radio inspections not just as an IT upgrade, but as a collective change requiring commitment to technology, training, and supportive policy.

6.3 Contribution to Knowledge and Practice

This study makes important contributions to both academic knowledge and maritime industry practice. From a scholarly perspective, it addresses a clear gap by examining the digitalization of marine radio inspections – an area previously under-researched. The findings validate and extend well-known models of technology adoption and organizational change into this new context. The prominence of perceived usefulness and ease-of-use among inspectors echoes the Technology Acceptance Model, while the influence of early adopters and the need for leadership support reflect Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory and Kotter's change management principles. By demonstrating that these concepts hold true in a safety-critical maritime domain, the research broadens the applicability of those theories beyond traditional settings.

From a practical standpoint, the research provides evidence that marine radio surveys can be streamlined through digital tools without compromising compliance or thoroughness. This serves as proof of concept that gives industry stakeholders confidence in adopting digital inspection methods. Moreover, the study's recommendations provide a concrete roadmap for implementation, translating the findings into actionable steps for inspectors, ship operators, and regulators.

Emphasizing comprehensive training and change management directly addresses the human factors identified as barriers, and urging regulators to formally accept electronic records targets the policy gap revealed by the study. By showing that vessels using digital record-keeping experienced fewer deficiencies and quicker

issue resolution, the project also builds a business case for investing in these technologies as part of maritime safety management. In summary, the project bridges theory and practice: it advances academic understanding of technology adoption in maritime operations while providing practical guidance that can lead to more efficient, consistent, and safe inspection processes.

6.4 Future Research Directions

While this project provided valuable insights, further research is needed to broaden and deepen the understanding of digital marine inspections. Promising directions for future work include:

- **Broader and Longitudinal Studies:** Use larger, more diverse samples and conduct longitudinal studies that track digital tool adoption over time. This would improve generalizability and capture how impacts evolve as technology use matures.
- **In-depth Organizational Case Studies:** Conduct qualitative case studies of specific organizations or ports that have implemented digital inspection systems. In-depth insights into training approaches, change management efforts, and cultural adjustments (including any setbacks) would yield practical lessons to guide others through similar transitions.
- **Emerging Technologies for Inspections:** Explore emerging technologies (e.g., AI-driven smart checklists or remote inspection via drones and live video feeds) to further enhance or transform the inspection process. Such research should assess whether these innovations can extend the benefits of digital inspections or change the role of the inspector in the future.
- **Impact on Safety Outcomes:** Quantitatively evaluate the long-term effects of digital tool adoption on safety and compliance outcomes. For instance, analyse industry data to determine if greater digital tool usage correlates with fewer equipment failures, lower incidence of radio-related problems at sea, or reduced

deficiency rates in port State control inspections. Demonstrating a clear link between digital practices and improved safety outcomes would provide strong evidence for continued investment in these technologies.

Such studies would also help address this study's limitations (for example, its limited scope and timeframe) and keep pace with technological developments. Ongoing research will ensure the maritime sector is guided by up-to-date evidence on leveraging digital innovation to improve safety, efficiency, and compliance.

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8. Appendices

Appendix A: Interview Guide

Introduction: This semi-structured interview guide was used to gather qualitative insights from different stakeholders in the marine radio inspection process. The interviews were tailored to four groups – **Marine Radio Inspectors, Ship Operators, Classification Society Representatives, and Maritime Regulatory Officials** – to ensure diverse perspectives. Questions covered current practices, experiences with digital tools, perceived benefits, challenges (including organizational policies, training, IT infrastructure, and regulatory factors), and future outlook. Each interviewee was encouraged to elaborate on their responses. All interviews concluded with an invitation for additional comments or suggestions.

Interview Questions for Marine Radio Inspectors (Surveyors)

1. **Current Inspection Process:** *Can you describe how you currently conduct a marine radio inspection?* (Probe: steps involved, tools or documentation used, any digital devices currently in use)
2. **Experience with Digital Tools:** *Are you using any digital tools or software as part of the inspection process?* (If **Yes**: Which tools and for what purpose? e.g., digital checklists on tablets, platforms like **Kaiko Systems** or **CloudVisit**, GMDSS testing apps. If **No**: Are you aware of such tools and why haven't you adopted them?)
3. **Perceived Benefits:** *What benefits do you find (or anticipate) in using digital tools for radio inspections?* (e.g., saving time, improved accuracy of reports, easier data logging, better compliance tracking)
4. **Ease of Use and Training:** *How easy or challenging have you found it to learn and use these digital tools?* (Probe: user-friendliness of the tools. **Training** – Have you received any training or guidance on using them? Was it adequate?)
5. **Organizational Policies:** *Does your organization or employer have any policies or guidelines regarding the use of digital tools during inspections?* (If **Yes**: How do these policies influence your use of such tools? If **No**: Has the lack of policy affected your adoption of digital methods?)

6. **IT Infrastructure Readiness:** *Is the necessary IT infrastructure in place to support digital inspections in your work?* (Probe: Do you have reliable devices, software, and internet connectivity on site or onboard ships to use digital tools effectively? Any technical issues faced?)
7. **Regulatory Considerations:** *Do current regulations or survey requirements affect your ability or willingness to use digital tools?* (Probe: Are there regulatory **challenges** such as requirements for physical signatures or original documents, or concerns from flag states about digital records? How do you navigate these?)
8. **Challenges and Concerns:** *What other challenges have you encountered or foresee with adopting digital inspection tools?* (e.g., resistance from colleagues, data security/**cybersecurity concerns**, reliability of digital devices in the marine environment)
9. **Future Adoption and Outlook:** *How likely are you to continue using or expand the use of digital tools in your future inspections?* (Probe: Are you personally **willing to adopt** more digital solutions? What would encourage greater adoption – e.g., better tools, more training, regulatory acceptance? Do you envision digital tools becoming a standard part of radio surveys in the near future?)

Interview Questions for Ship Operators (Crew and Managers)

1. **Inspection Experience Overview:** *Can you describe the typical process of a marine radio inspection on your vessel or within your fleet?* (Probe: How are you involved, and what preparation or follow-up is required on your side?)
2. **Exposure to Digital Tools:** *Have inspectors or crew used any digital tools during these radio inspections?* (If **Yes**: Which tools have you observed – for example, electronic checklists, **Kaiko Systems** reports, remote inspection via **CloudVisit**, etc.? How was the experience from your perspective? If **No**: Are you aware of such technologies and what is your impression of them?)
3. **Perceived Benefits:** *What benefits do you think digital tools bring to the inspection process for ship operators like yourself?* (e.g., faster inspections, less paperwork onboard, immediate feedback on compliance, improved record-keeping)
4. **Operational Challenges:** *Have you encountered any challenges when digital tools are used during an inspection?* (Probe: Any difficulties for the crew in using or

accommodating these tools? Issues like lack of familiarity, interruptions to operations, etc.)

5. **Organizational Policies & Support:** *Does your company have any policies or programs encouraging the use of digital tools for inspections or onboard maintenance?* (If **Yes**: What do they entail – for instance, mandated use of certain software or digital record systems? If **No** or **Not sure**: How do you personally feel about the company's stance on digitalization?)
6. **Training and Readiness:** *Have ship personnel received training on digital inspection systems or related digital competencies?* (Probe: Examples of training on using inspection apps or maintaining electronic logs. **IT infrastructure** – Is the ship's infrastructure (internet connectivity, onboard IT systems) sufficient to support digital inspections or remote attendance by surveyors?)
7. **Regulatory and Compliance View:** *From your perspective, are there any regulatory hurdles or concerns with inspectors using digital tools?* (Probe: Do port state control officers or flag surveyors accept digital evidence or do they still require paper? Any uncertainty about compliance using digital records?)
8. **Cybersecurity Concerns:** *Do you have any concerns about data security or cybersecurity when digital systems are used during inspections?* (e.g., risk of sensitive ship data being transmitted; how does the company address such concerns?)
9. **Future Perspective:** *Would you be open to more digitalization in the inspection process moving forward?* (Probe: **Willingness to adopt** – For instance, would you support remote inspections or the use of advanced digital reporting tools? What would increase your comfort or buy-in for such changes? Any suggestions for smoother adoption?)

Interview Questions for Classification Society Representatives (Surveyors/Managers)

1. **Current Survey Practices:** *How does your classification society currently conduct GMDSS/marine radio surveys and inspections?* (Probe: Are there digital components in your standard practice, such as electronic reporting systems or data management platforms?)
2. **Use of Digital Tools:** *Is your society implementing or experimenting with digital tools for radio inspections?* (If **Yes**: Please describe – e.g., using tablets for checklist

recording, proprietary software, or partnerships with solutions like **Kaiko Systems**. How widely used are these tools among your surveyors? If **No**: Is there discussion or interest in adopting such tools in the future?)

3. **Perceived Benefits:** *What benefits do digital tools offer to classification surveys, from your organization's perspective?* (e.g., standardized data collection, improved accuracy and consistency across surveyors, efficiency in issuing reports or certificates, data analytics on survey findings over time)
4. **Surveyor Training and Adoption:** *Have your surveyors been trained to use digital inspection platforms or software?* (Probe: Details on any **digital training programs** provided, and whether surveyors find the tools **easy to use**. How do you support surveyors who are less tech-savvy? Any feedback received from them?)
5. **Organizational Policies:** *What internal policies or guidelines does the classification society have regarding digital inspection methods?* (Probe: Are there official directives encouraging digital data capture or remote inspection? Any quality control or data security policies related to using such tools?)
6. **IT Infrastructure & Systems:** *Is the IT infrastructure of your organization ready to support a fully digital inspection workflow?* (e.g., Do surveyors have the necessary hardware and software? Is there an integrated backend system to store and share digital survey results with clients and flag authorities? Any challenges in implementation such as system compatibility or cost?)
7. **Regulatory and Client Acceptance:** *How do regulatory bodies and clients (ship owners/operators) view the use of digital tools in class surveys?* (Probe: Have you encountered **regulatory challenges** – for instance, flag states not accepting remote survey results, or needing to provide paper documentation in addition to digital? How about client buy-in – are ship owners comfortable with digital reporting, or do some prefer traditional methods?)
8. **Challenges and Risks:** *What challenges has your society faced in the move toward digital inspection tools?* (e.g., data/cybersecurity concerns with storing inspection data on cloud systems, initial costs, change management among staff, ensuring accuracy of digital records, interoperability between different systems)
9. **Future Outlook:** *What is the future strategy of your classification society regarding digital tools for inspections?* (Probe: Does the society plan to expand the use of such tools? In what areas? **Willingness to adopt** – Are surveyors and management on board

with these changes? How do you see digital tools and maybe innovations like AI or IoT shaping radio inspections in the next 5–10 years?)

Interview Questions for Maritime Regulatory Officials (Flag/Port State Authorities)

1. **Role and Perspective:** *Can you describe your role in relation to marine radio inspections and oversight? (Probe: Involvement in flag state surveys, port state control inspections, or setting inspection standards/policies)*
2. **View on Digital Tools:** *What is your perspective on the use of digital tools in conducting and reporting marine radio inspections? (Probe: Awareness of technologies like remote inspection platforms (e.g., **CloudVisit**) or digital reporting systems used by inspectors or class societies. Do you find them beneficial for compliance monitoring?)*
3. **Current Policy/Guidance:** *Has your administration introduced any policies, guidelines or pilot programs regarding digital inspections or electronic record-keeping? (If **Yes**: What do this entail and how are they being implemented? If **No**: Is there ongoing discussion about updating regulations to accommodate digital methods?)*
4. **Acceptance Criteria:** *Under what conditions would your authority accept a digitally conducted or digitally recorded radio inspection? (Probe: Would a remote inspection or an inspection report generated via a digital tool be accepted as equivalent to a traditional inspection? Any examples or case-by-case allowances, such as those made during COVID-19 for remote surveys?)*
5. **Regulatory Challenges:** *What challenges do regulators face with the advent of digital inspection tools? (e.g., ensuring **cybersecurity** and authenticity of digital reports, lack of international standards or guidelines, need for inspector training in new methods, verifying that digital tools meet IMO requirements)*
6. **Industry Readiness:** *In your view, are the industry and its IT infrastructure ready for a shift toward digital inspections? (Probe: Do most ships have capability for remote connectivity if needed? Are classification societies providing data in formats you can use? How is the regulator’s own IT system set up to receive or review digital inspection data?)*
7. **Compliance and Enforcement:** *How do digital tools impact compliance enforcement and record-keeping from the regulator’s side? (Probe: Do digital records make it easier*

or harder to audit and enforce standards? Are there concerns about fraud or data manipulation in electronic records versus traditional logs?)

8. **Future Regulatory Outlook:** *Do you foresee changes in regulations to accommodate or encourage digital tools in marine inspections?* (Probe: Is the administration working with international bodies (IMO, IACS) on this? How **willing** are regulators to adopt innovations in this area? What timeline or steps do you envision for broader acceptance?)
9. **Support and Collaboration:** *How can regulators support the safe and effective adoption of digital inspection tools?* (Probe: possible initiatives like certification of specific digital tools, training for inspectors on digital methods, developing cybersecurity standards for maritime digital systems)

Closing Question for All Interviewees: *Do you have any other comments or suggestions regarding the use of digital tools in marine radio inspections that we haven't covered?* (This prompt gave interviewees an opportunity to add any insight, concerns, or recommendations beyond the structured questions.)

Appendix B: Survey Questionnaire

This survey aims to gather perspectives on adopting digital tools in marine radio (GMDSS) inspections from various stakeholders (inspectors, ship operators, classification society personnel, and regulators). The questionnaire is structured around key factors from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory, including perceived usefulness, ease of use, and compatibility (en.wikipedia.org) (en.wikipedia.org). The insights will help identify benefits, challenges, and readiness for digital transformation in the marine radio inspection process.

Participant Anonymity and Consent: No personally identifying information (such as names or contact details) is collected in this survey. In sensitive contexts, ensuring anonymity is crucial to encouraging candid feedback (lattice.com). All responses will be kept confidential and used only for academic research. Participation is voluntary – you may skip any question or stop at any time. By proceeding, you indicate your informed consent to participate in this study.

For the purposes of this survey, “digital tools” refers to any software, devices, or technology used to assist or streamline the marine radio inspection process (e.g., electronic checklist applications, mobile/tablet apps for inspections, remote inspection video systems, IoT-based monitoring devices, cloud-based record systems, etc.)

Participant Information

Q1. What is your stakeholder role? (*Select one*)

- Marine Radio Inspector/Surveyor** (conducting GMDSS radio inspections onboard)
- Ship Operator/Crew Member** (ship **personnel** responsible for facilitating inspections)
- Classification Society Personnel** (class surveyor or manager involved in radio surveys)
- Regulatory Authority Representative** (maritime regulator overseeing compliance)
- Other:** Please *specify* _____

Q2. How many years of experience do you have in the maritime industry (in roles related to marine radio inspections or operations)? (*Select one*)

- Less than 5 years
- 5–10 years
- 11–20 years
- More than 20 years

Q3. Have you personally used any digital tools as part of the marine radio inspection process? (*Select one*)

- Yes** – I have used digital tool(s) in conducting, preparing for, or reporting on radio inspections.
- No** – I have not used digital tools in the context of radio inspections.

Q4. [*If Q3 = Yes*] Which digital tool(s) have you used or encountered? (*Select all that apply or describe*)

- Mobile or tablet-based inspection applications (electronic checklists/forms)
- Remote inspection technologies (live video inspections, remote access systems)
- IoT sensors or automated monitoring systems for radio equipment
- Cloud platforms or software for managing inspection records/certificates
- Other digital tools: *please specify* _____

Perceived Benefits of Digital Tools

Q5. Perceived Usefulness – Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about the **benefits** of using digital tools in marine radio inspections.

(Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Using digital tools can increase the efficiency of the marine radio inspection process.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digital tools improve the accuracy of radio inspection results by reducing human errors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digital tools make it easier to ensure compliance with GMDSS/SOLAS requirements during inspections.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The benefits of using digital tools in radio inspections outweigh any potential drawbacks .	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Perceived Ease of Use and Training

Q6. Usability – Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about the **ease of use** of digital inspection tools and related training. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Ease of use: I find digital inspection tools <i>easy to use</i> in the context of marine radio surveys.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ease of learning: It is <i>easy to learn</i> how to operate the digital tools for radio inspections.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
User-friendliness: Using these digital tools does <i>not require highly specialized technical expertise</i> (average personnel can use them effectively).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Training adequacy: <i>Adequate training is available</i> for personnel to use digital inspection tools effectively.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Organizational and Technical Support

Q7. Organizational Context – Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about **organizational support and infrastructure** for digital tools. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Compatibility: Digital tools are <i>compatible with our existing inspection workflows</i> (they fit well into current processes).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Work practice fit: Using digital tools <i>aligns with my organization's practices and policies</i> for inspections.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
IT infrastructure: We have the <i>necessary IT infrastructure</i> (hardware, software, reliable internet connectivity) to support digital tools for inspections.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Management support: <i>Management supports</i> the adoption of digital tools for marine radio inspections (leadership encourages or endorses their use).	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Regulatory Environment

Q8. Regulatory Readiness – Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about the **regulatory environment** for digital inspection tools. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Regulatory support: The current <i>regulatory framework supports the use of digital tools</i> in marine radio inspections (regulations allow or recognize digital methods).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Guidance: <i>Regulators provide clear guidelines</i> on how digital tools can be used to meet inspection requirements.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Acceptance: Inspection results obtained through digital tools are <i>recognized as valid by regulatory authorities</i> (digital records/reports are accepted by regulators).	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Overall Adoption and Feedback

	1	2	3	4	5
Q9					
Overall, I support the increased use of digital tools in marine radio inspections.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Q10					
I intend to adopt digital tools in my work related to radio inspections in the future (<i>either by personally using them or by advocating for their use in my organization</i>).	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Q11. Additional Comments: Please provide any **additional comments or suggestions** regarding the use of digital tools in marine radio inspections.

Appendix C: Sample Inspection Record Template

This template covers the required Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) radio inspection items for SOLAS-compliant vessels (passenger ships and cargo ships ≥ 300 GT). It integrates best practices from multiple classification society checklists (ABS, DNV, RINA, LR) and IMO survey guidelines. The form is structured as a compliance checklist to document each item, with fields for marking compliance (Yes/No or N/A) and space for remarks. It is designed for use as a digital form or printable report.

Instructions: Mark each item as **Yes** (compliant/satisfactory) or **No** (non-compliant), or **N/A** if not applicable. Provide details or remarks for any **No** responses or other observations. All checks should be performed in accordance with SOLAS Chapter IV requirements and applicable IMO performance standards. Attach additional pages or electronic notes as needed for explanations. Dates should be recorded in DD/MM/YYYY format.

REPORT ON NEW / PERIODICAL SURVEY OF GMDSS RADIO INSTALLATION				Job Id:	
				Date of issue:	
SHIPS FITTED WITH GMDSS RADIO INSTALLATION (Radio communications installation requirements for passenger ships irrespective of size and ships of 300 tons gross tonnage and upwards complying with new Chap. IV, SOLAS 1974 and its Amendments)					
1. Particulars of ship					
Vessel Name:			Call Sign:		
IMO Number:			MMSI:		
Flag State/Port of Registry:			Gross Tonnage:		
Classification Society:			Survey Location/Port		
Survey Date:			Surveyor Name:		
GMDSS Sea Area Certified			<input type="checkbox"/> A1 <input type="checkbox"/> A2 <input type="checkbox"/> A3 <input type="checkbox"/> A4		
Radio Maintenance Method (SOLAS IV/15):			<input type="checkbox"/> Duplication of Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Shore-based maintenance <input type="checkbox"/> At-sea maintenance		
2. Radio Power Supply and Reserve Energy (SOLAS II-1/42, II-1/43; SOLAS IV/13)					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Main source of electrical power for radio installations (ship's main power supply operational for all radio equipment)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Emergency source of electrical power (emergency generator or equivalent backup) provided and functional – capable of supporting radio communications for required duration (36 hours for passenger ships / 18 hours for cargo ships) (SOLAS II-1/42 or II-1/43)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Automatic changeover to emergency or reserve power upon loss of main power (no interruption to radio equipment power) (SOLAS /13.3)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Reserve source of energy (dedicated radio battery) suitably installed (proper location, ventilation, and protection) for radio installations, if required (SOLAS IV/13.2; IV/13.5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Reserve battery capacity adequate for minimum required duration (able to operate all required radio equipment for 1 hour if an emergency source is provided, or 6 hours if no emergency source) (SOLAS IV/13.2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Reserve battery charging system operational (automatic charger capable of recharging battery to full capacity within 10 hours) (SOLAS IV/13.4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Periodic capacity testing of reserve battery performed (e.g. annual battery discharge test with records) to verify actual capacity meets requirements (SOLAS IV/13.6.2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Reserve battery performance under load acceptable (battery voltage and discharge current within limits with battery off-charge under maximum radio load) (SOLAS IV/13.7)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Adequate illumination of radio control panel/controls by a reliable, permanently installed light source independent of main and emergency power (for operation in case of total power failure) (SOLAS IV/13.3)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Continuous provision of ship's position information to all two-way radio communication equipment is ensured (automatic positioning data available even if main/emergency power fails) (SOLAS IV/18)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
3. Radio Equipment Installation and Operation					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
VHF radio installation, capable of DSC alerting on VHF Channel 70 and voice communication on Channel 16 (and Ch.13/Ch.6) (SOLAS IV/7).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
MF radio installation – Capable of DSC on 2,187.5 kHz and radiotelephony on 2,182 kHz (required for Sea Area A2 and beyond) (SOLAS IV/9).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
MF/HF radio installation – Capable of DSC and NBDP (telex) on all distress and safety HF bands (required for Sea Areas A3/A4) (SOLAS IV/10, IV/11).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Satellite ship earth station (Inmarsat-C or other GMDSS-approved SATCOM) – Installed and operational (for Sea Area A3 coverage) (SOLAS IV/10).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Continuous watch receivers – VHF DSC watch receiver on Ch.70 and MF DSC watch on 2,187.5 kHz (if A2/A3) are provided and functioning (audible alarms for distress calls) (SOLAS IV/12).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Duplicate equipment (if required by maintenance method or sea area) – Second independent set of critical equipment provided (e.g. dual VHF, dual MF/HF) for redundancy (SOLAS IV/15; MSC Res.A.702(17)).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

4. Distress Alerting and Emergency Communication Devices					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Satellite EPIRB (float-free type) (<i>SOLAS IV/15.9; SOLAS III/6.2.2</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Second EPIRB (if applicable) (<i>SOLAS IV/6; SOLAS IV/15.9</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
EPIRB Registration & Encoding (<i>SOLAS IV/7</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Search and Rescue Radar Transponder (SART) (<i>SOLAS IV/7; SOLAS III/6.2.2</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
AIS SART (<i>SOLAS IV/7; SOLAS III/6.2.2</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Two-way Portable GMDSS VHF (<i>SOLAS III/6.2.1; SOLAS IV/4</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
5. Maritime Safety Information (MSI) Receivers					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
NAVTEX receiver (518 kHz) (<i>SOLAS IV/7.1.4</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Enhanced Group Call (EGC) receiver (Inmarsat SafetyNET) (<i>SOLAS IV/7.1.5</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
HF NBDP receiver (HF direct-printing telegraphy) (<i>SOLAS IV/7.1.5</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
6. Bridge Interface and Navigational Inputs					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Position input (GNSS) – A GPS or other Global Navigation Satellite System receiver is provided position data to the GMDSS equipment (for automatic inclusion in distress alerts) (<i>SOLAS IV/18</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Continuous position updates – Confirm ship’s position is automatically updated to all relevant radio equipment (DSC controllers, Inmarsat terminal, etc.), or manual input procedure in place (updates at intervals ≤4 hours)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Distress alert panel at bridge (Conning position) – Fitted and functional (enables transmission of distress alert from bridge) (<i>SOLAS IV/6.4</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Distress alerts audible/visual alarm on bridge – Fitted (indicates reception of a distress alert on GMDSS equipment) (<i>SOLAS IV/6.5</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

7. Documentation and Certificates					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Ship's Radio Station Licence – Valid national radio license on board (ship's callsign and radio frequencies authorized).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Radio Certificate (Cargo Ship Safety Radio Certificate or Passenger Ship Safety Certificate) – Valid and current (annual GMDSS survey dates endorsed)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
GMDSS Radio Operator Certificates – At least two certified operators for ships ≥300 GT (GOC/ROC as required by voyage area) (SOLAS IV/16).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Shore-based maintenance agreement (certificate or contract for shore-based GMDSS maintenance is on board and valid)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
GMDSS Radio Logbook – Up-to-date with required entries (tests, distress communications, routine drills, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Required publications – Latest GMDSS references available (e.g. ITU Lists of Coast Stations/Ship Stations, IMO GMDSS manuals, NAVAREA warnings)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Equipment type-approval certificates – Radio equipment compliance (where applicable) are on file (confirm each GMDSS equipment model is type-approved per IMO/IEC standards).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
8. General Arrangements and Additional Requirements					
Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Antennas – All radio antennas (VHF, MF/HF, GPS, Inmarsat) are securely mounted, free of damage/corrosion, and clear of obstructions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Cabling and grounding – GMDSS wiring is intact and properly routed. Ground connections are secure; no sign of wear or overheating on cables. Adequate protection and labelling of all radio-related cables.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Emergency operating instructions – Distress and emergency communication instructions are posted in English and the working language (on bridge and at radio station)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Bridge-to-bridge communications – VHF channel 13 (navigational safety channel) is operational from the bridge (SOLAS V/7). Verify a dedicated or primary VHF can operate on Ch.13 for collision avoidance communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Item Description	Compliance			Serial Number	Remarks / Expiry
	Yes	No	NA		
Identification and markings – The ship’s radio call sign, IMO number and MMSI are visibly posted near the radio console 【27†L93-L100】 . GMDSS station labels and operating licenses are displayed as required.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Additional requirements (Flag State or Polar Code) – If applicable, vessel complies with any extra radio requirements (e.g. Polar waters equipment: an EPIRB and SART for each lifeboat, additional two-way VHF’s in survival craft)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
<p>Surveyor/Inspector Verification: I hereby verify that the above items have been inspected in accordance with SOLAS requirements and applicable class guidelines. All deficiencies are noted in the Remarks.</p> <p>Name of Surveyor: _____ Signature: _____</p> <p>Name of Radio Inspector: _____ Signature: _____</p> <p>Date: _____ Port: _____</p> <p>Official Stamp: _____</p>					

Appendix D: Reflective Summary (Diary Extracts)

Researcher's Reflective Journal – Key Excerpts

- **Week 1 (January 2025): *Initiation and Literature Review*** – I began the project by reviewing literature on marine radio inspections and digital tools. It became evident that while general maritime digitalization is well-documented, there is a niche regarding radio-specific inspection processes. This realization helped refine my research questions to focus on how digital checklists and databases might address the pain points identified in past studies. I noted feeling both excited about the topic and cautious about finding enough academic sources on this specialized subject.
- **Week 4 (February 2025): *Interview Preparation and Pilot*** – I developed the interview guide and conducted a pilot interview with a fellow student to test the questions (Appendix A). The pilot highlighted the need to clarify certain terms (e.g., “digital tools” needed examples). After revisions, I scheduled interviews with two experienced marine radio inspectors. I was a bit nervous before the first expert interview, but it went smoothly. In my diary, I reflected on the importance of active listening and probing for detailed examples during the interviews, which proved valuable as the interviewees shared insightful anecdotes.
- **Week 6 (Mid-February 2025): *Conducting Interviews*** – I completed all interviews and was struck by a common theme: inspectors acknowledged the potential of digital tools, yet many still relied on paper due to regulatory habit and reliability concerns. I wrote in my journal about one interview where the inspector demonstrated a tablet-based app he’s been testing – this real-world illustration reinforced some of the literature findings about efficiency gains. I also reflected on my own growth in confidence; by the final interview, I was more adept at guiding the conversation while letting the participant speak freely.
- **Week 8 (Late February 2025): *Survey Roll-out and Early Analysis*** – The online survey (Appendix B) was circulated, and responses started coming in. I noted initial trends in my diary: for instance, a surprising number of older inspectors expressed interest in learning digital tools, contradicting an assumption I had that only younger

professionals are keen on tech adoption. I began transcribing interview recordings and organizing data. This phase was overwhelming as I juggled qualitative coding and monitoring survey results, but I kept a structured schedule. A diary entry this week highlights how creating a coding framework for interview data helped me feel more in control of the qualitative analysis.

- **Week 10 (March 2025): *Data Synthesis and Reflection*** – With the survey closed and interviews transcribed, I spent this week synthesizing findings. In my reflection, I wrote about the interplay between quantitative survey data and qualitative insights: the survey quantified that about 70% of respondents saw time-saving benefits with digital tools, and the interviews provided context, explaining that these tools cut down paperwork after inspections. I also reflected on the challenges: one diary note reads, “*Encountered conflicting viewpoints – need to honestly report reluctance due to regulatory uncertainties, even though I personally believe in digital benefits.*” This reminded me to remain objective. As I drafted the discussion chapter, I included a personal perspective on how the project improved my understanding of change management in a traditional industry. By the end of the project, my diary entries conveyed a sense of accomplishment and an appreciation for the value of combining field experience with academic research.